

Algebraic Pandiagonal Striped and Semi-Striped Magic Squares of Orders 4 to 12

The whole work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17599>

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Abstract

This work brings **algebraic pandiagonal striped** and **semi-striped** magic squares of orders 4 to 12 for the **reduced entries**. The even orders are **striped** magic squares and odd orders are **semi-striped** magic squares. By **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These entries are non-sequential positive and negative numbers. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of the entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe decimal or fractional values of the entries depending on the types of magic squares. By **striped** magic square we understand that it is composed of equal width strips of order 2. The change is only in the lengths of the magic rectangles. There are three types of magic squares studied here. For simplicity we call them as **cyclic-type**, **flat-type** and **corner-type**. This type of work is not known before in the literature of magic square. It is brought for the first time here. For the study on sequential entries magic squares i.e., the idea of **double-digit bordered** magic squares for sequential number entries is studied by the author [32]. This work is for non-sequential entries. Moreover, in this work the magic rectangles are considered as **cyclic**, **flat** or **cornered**. In case of odd orders, except the magic square of orders 3 or 5, all others are magic rectangles of width 2. The change is always in length of magic rectangles. These kind of magic squares we call as **semi-striped**. For similar kind of work for different orders in different styles and designs, the readers are suggested to see author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21].

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1 Introduction

This work brings **algebraic pandiagonal striped** and **semi-striped** magic squares of orders 4 to 12 for the **reduced entries**. By **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These entries are non-sequential positive and negative numbers. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe decimal or fractional values of the entries depending on the types of magic squares. The work **double-digit** or **double-layer bordered** and **cornered** magic squares. In case of **double-digit**, we have two different ways of writing. One is **cyclic-type** and another is **flat-type**. In case of **cyclic-type**, each layer has four equal sums magic rectangles and in case of **flat-type**, we have two big and two small magic rectangles in each layer. Including the **corner-type**, we have each order in three different types of magic squares. In case of odd orders, except the magic square of orders 3 or 5, all others are magic rectangles of width 2. The change is always in length of magic rectangles. These kind of magic squares we call as **semi-striped**. For similar kind of work for different orders in different styles and designs, the readers are suggested to see author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21].

We know that magic sum of a magic square of order n having 1 to n^2 number of entries is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}$$

In this work the entries are written as variables and their combinations. Instead of sequential entries, we have non-sequential entries. These can be positive, negative or decimal numbers. Every result is followed by an example.

For even order magic squares work is in terms of equal width magic rectangles calling **striped** magic squares. For odd orders except one magic square of order 3 or 5 all are magic rectangles of equal width. The idea of **double-digit** for magic squares for sequential number entries studied by the author [32] for the first time. This work is for non-sequential entries. Moreover, we have considered the magic rectangles in three types, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** or **corner**. For similar kind of work for different orders in different styles and ways, the readers are suggested to see author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. For **double-digit** work for **sequential** entries refer [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32].

2 Algebraic Pandiagonal Striped Magic Squares

The section bring results and examples of **reduced entries algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic squares even orders from 4 to 12. These are of three types: **cyclic-type**, **flat-type** and **corner-type**. For orders 4 and 6, we don't have this kind of classification.

2.1 Algebraic Pandiagonal Striped Magic Square of Order 4

Result 2.1. An *algebraic pandiagonal striped* magic square of order 4 is given by

$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$
$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	a_2	a_3
a_2	a_3	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$
$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1

- Details**

It is pandiagonal magic square of order 4 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2. In this case the magic sum is given as $S_{4 \times 4} := 3m$, where m is the width of the of the magic rectangle. See below an example:

Example 2.1. Below is an example of *algebraic pandiagonal striped* magic square of order 4 based on Result 2.1:

	pan	46	46	46	46
46	25	11	8	2	46
46	-2	12	15	21	46
46	15	21	-2	12	46
	8	2	25	11	46
	46	46	46	46	46

In this case the magic sum is $S_{4 \times 4} := 46, m := 23$. As written above the **strips** are of equal lengths and widths. See below:

25	11	8	2	46
-2	12	15	21	46
23	23	23	23	
15	21	-2	12	46
8	2	25	11	46
23	23	23	23	

2.2 Algebraic Pandiagonal Striped Magic Squares of Order 6

Below are three different ways of writing **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 6.

2.2.1 First-Type

Result 2.2. An **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 6 is given by

A1	m-A1	A5	A6	$A4+m-A7+A1-A5-A6$	$m-A4+A7-A1$
A2	m-A2	m-A5	m-A6	$A7-A1+A5+A6-A4$	$A4-A7+A1$
A3	m-A3	$A5+A2+A3-m$	$(1/2)*m-A7+A1$	$(1/2)*m+A4-A5$	$2*m+A7-A2-A3-A4-A1$
$(3/2)*m-A7-A6$	$A7+A6-(1/2)*m$	$2*m-A2-A3-A5$	$(1/2)*m+A7-A1$	$(1/2)*m-A4+A5$	$A2+A3-m+A4+A1-A7$
$(3/2)*m-A1-A2-A3+A7+A6-A4$	$A1+A2+A3-(1/2)*m-A7-A6+A4$	$m-A4+A5-A1$	$A4+A1-A7+A3-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A5-A3$	A7
A4	m-A4	$A4-A5+A1$	$(3/2)*m-A4-A1+A7-A3$	$A5-(1/2)*m+A3$	m-A7

bullet **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 6, where there there three equal sums strips of orders 2×4 and one strip of order 2×6 . The magic sum of order 6 is $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangles. In order to avoid decimal entries, we must have m as multiple of 2. See below an example:

Example 2.2. Below is an example of **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic squares of order 6 based on Result 2.2:

	pan	102	102	102	102	102	102
102	10	24	22	25	-12	33	102
102	13	21	12	9	46	1	102
102	16	18	17	-1	14	38	102
102	-2	36	17	35	20	-4	102
102	46	-12	27	0	13	28	102
	19	15	7	34	21	6	102
	102	102	102	102	102	102	102

In this case the magic sum of order 6 is $S_{6 \times 6} := 102$, where 34 is the width of the strip. The lengths are respectively 68 and 102. Check below the width and lengths fo the strips, i.e., of magic rectangles:

			22	25	-12	33	68
10	24	34	12	9	46	1	68
13	21	34	34	34	34	34	
16	18	34	17	-1	14	38	68
-2	36	34	17	35	20	-4	68
46	-12	34	34	34	34	34	
19	15	34	27	0	13	28	68
102	102		7	34	21	6	68
			34	34	34	34	

2.2.2 Second-Type

Result 2.3. An **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 6 is given by

$(12/5)*m-a2-2*a1-a4$	$a1$	$(3/5)*m$	$a2$	$a4+a1-a3$	$a3$
$2*a1-(7/5)*m+a4+a2$	$m-a1$	$(2/5)*m$	$m-a2$	$m+a3-a4-a1$	$m-a3$
$(9/10)*m-a1$	$(3/2)*m-a4-a2$	$a4+a2+a1-(9/10)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a4-a1$	$2*a4-a3+a2-(3/2)*m+2*a1$	$(3/2)*m-a4-a2+a3-a1$
$(1/10)*m+a1$	$a4+a2-(1/2)*m$	$(19/10)*m-a4-a2-a1$	$a4+a1-(1/2)*m$	$(5/2)*m-2*a4-a2-2*a1+a3$	$a4+a2-a3+a1-(1/2)*m$
$(12/5)*m+a3-2*a4-a2-2*a1$	$a4+a1-a3$	$(3/5)*m-a4+a3$	$a4+a2-a3$	$a1$	$a4$
$2*a4+a2+2*a1-a3-(7/5)*m$	$m+a3-a4-a1$	$a4+(2/5)*m-a3$	$m-a4-a2+a3$	$m-a1$	$m-a4$

• Details

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 6, where there are three equal sums strips of orders 2×6 . The magic sum of order 6 is $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangles. See below an example:

Example 2.3. Below is an example of **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic squares of order 6 based on Result 2.3:

	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	40	10	24	15	13	18	120
120	0	30	16	25	27	22	120
120	26	24	10	29	-1	32	120
120	14	16	30	11	41	8	120
120	37	13	21	18	10	21	120
	3	27	19	22	30	19	120
	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

In this case the magic sum of order 6 is $S_{6 \times 6} := 120$, where 40 is the width of the strip. The lengths are same as of magic sum. Check below the width and lengths of the strips, i.e., of magic rectangles. All three are of equal sums:

40	10	24	15	13	18	120
0	30	16	25	27	22	120
40	40	40	40	40	40	
26	24	10	29	-1	32	120
14	16	30	11	41	8	120
40	40	40	40	40	40	
37	13	21	18	10	21	120
3	27	19	22	30	19	120
40	40	40	40	40	40	

Remark 2.1. We observe the difference between the Results 2.2 and 2.3. The Result 2.2 don't require any condition, while the Results 2.3 requires that m should be divisible by 10 to avoid decimal or fractional entries.

2.2.3 Third-Type: Cornered

Result 2.4. An algebraic pandiagonal striped magic square of order 6 is given by

$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	a_4	$m-a_4$
$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	a_2	a_3	$(1/2)*m+a_2-a_5$	$(1/2)*m-a_2+a_5$
a_2	a_3	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	$(1/2)*m-a_3-a_2+a_1+a_5$	$a_3+a_2+(1/2)*m-a_1-a_5$
$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_4-a_1+a_3$	$a_4+a_1-a_3$
$(1/2)*m-a_4-a_1+a_3+a_2$	$a_1-a_2+a_5$	$m-a_5$	$a_4+(1/2)*m-a_3$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$
$a_4+(1/2)*m+a_1-a_3-a_2$	$m-a_1+a_2-a_5$	a_5	$(1/2)*m+a_3-a_4$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$

• **Details**

*It is similar to Result 2.2. In this case, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 is divided in two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×4 in the upper-left corner characterizing as **cornered** magic square of order 6. The magic sum of order 6 is $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangles. In this case, we have 3 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and one of order 2×6 . In order to avoid decimal entries, we must have m as multiple of 2. See below an example:*

Example 2.4. Below is an example of **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic squares of order 6 based on Result 2.4:

	pan	138	138	138	138	138	138
138	20	11	32	29	20	26	138
138	26	35	14	17	14	32	138
138	14	17	26	35	26	20	138
138	32	29	20	11	32	14	138
138	23	20	23	26	23	23	138
	23	26	23	20	23	23	138
	138	138	138	138	138	138	138

In this case the magic sum of order 6 is $S_{6 \times 6} := 138$, where 46 is the width of the strip. The lengths are 92 and 138. The magic square of order 4 is **pandiagonal** and is divided in two equal sums of magic rectangles of orders 2×4 . See below the the magic sum of order 4:

	pan	92	92	92	92
92	20	11	32	29	92
92	26	35	14	17	92
92	14	17	26	35	92
	32	29	20	11	92
	92	92	92	92	92

2.3 Algebraic Pandiagonal Striped Magic Squares of Order 8

Below are three different ways of writing **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 8, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.3.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.5. An **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 8 in **cyclic way** is given by

$6*m$	a_4	a_5	$a_1+a_9-2*a_4-a_5-4*m-a_6$	a_6	$a_4-a_1-a_9+m$	$5*m+a_8+a_4-a_2+a_{10}$	$a_2-4*m-a_{10}-a_8-a_4$
$m-6*m$	$m-a_4$	$m-a_5$	$5*m+a_6-a_1+2*a_4+a_5-a_9$	$m-a_6$	$a_1+a_9-a_4$	$m-a_{10}+a_2-a_8$	$a_{10}-a_2+a_8$
$a_4+a_2+a_3-a_{10}+a_6-a_1-a_9$	$a_{10}-a_6+a_1+a_9+m-a_4-a_2-a_3$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	$a_3+a_7-6*m+a_2+a_6-a_1-a_9$	$a_1+a_9+7*m-a_2-a_3-a_7-a_6$
a_{10}	$m-a_{10}$	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	a_2	a_3	$m-a_7$	a_7
$7*m-a_2-a_3-a_6+a_1$	$a_2+a_3+a_6-a_1-6*m$	a_2	a_3	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	$m+a_8-a_2-a_3-a_5+a_{10}-a_6-a_4+a_1+a_9$	$a_2+a_3+a_5-a_{10}+a_6+a_4-a_1-a_9-a_8$
a_9	$m-a_9$	$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$a_5-a_{10}+m-a_8$	$a_8-a_5+a_{10}$
$a_2-4*m-a_{10}-a_8-a_4$	$5*m+a_8+a_4-a_2+a_{10}$	$m-a_6+a_9-a_7$	$a_7+a_1-a_4$	$m-a_8$	$5*m+a_8+2*a_4+a_6-a_1-a_9$	$(-5*m)$	$m-a_4$
$a_{10}-a_2+a_8$	$m-a_{10}+a_2-a_8$	$a_7+a_6-a_9$	$m+a_4-a_7-a_1$	a_8	$a_1+a_9-4*m-a_8-2*a_4-a_6$	$6*m$	a_4

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 8 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4. This magic square of order 4 is composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . Since it is composed of all the strips of equal width, we can call it as an **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 8. Moreover, the external four strips are of equal sums, we can name it as a **algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 8. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See an example:

Example 2.5. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 8 based on Result 2.5:

	pan	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156
156	234	19	22	-197	25	14	269	-230	156
156	-195	20	17	236	14	25	-16	55	156
156	-8	47	19	10	26	23	-196	235	156
156	37	2	20	29	13	16	11	28	156
156	229	-190	13	16	20	29	56	-17	156
156	34	5	26	23	19	10	-7	46	156
156	-230	269	20	19	8	245	-195	20	156
	55	-16	19	20	31	-206	234	19	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

It is a **pandiagonal cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 8 with magic sum $S_{8 \times 8} := 156$. The magic sums of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 is given as $S_{4 \times 4} := 78$. See below the details:

	pan	78	78	78	78
78	19	10	26	23	78
78	20	29	13	16	78
78	13	16	20	29	78
	26	23	19	10	78
	78	78	78	78	78

2.3.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.6. An **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 8 in **cyclic way** is given by

$a_9+a_{10}+a_2+a_3+a_8+a_7-a_1-2*m$	a_4	a_5	$2*m-a_9-a_8-a_5$	a_6	$a_9+a_8-a_6$	$m-a_9-a_3+a_{11}$	$3*m-a_{10}-a_2-a_4-a_8-a_7+a_1-a_{11}$
$3*m-a_9-a_{10}-a_2-a_3-a_8-a_7+a_1$	$m-a_4$	$m-a_5$	$a_9+a_8+a_5-m$	$m-a_6$	$a_6+m-a_9-a_8$	$a_9+a_3-a_{11}$	$a_{10}+a_2+a_4+a_8+a_7-a_1+a_{11}-2*m$
$a_1-a_{11}+2*m-a_{10}-a_4-a_7$	$a_{10}-m+a_7-a_1+a_4+a_{11}$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	a_2	$m-a_2$	$m-a_7$	a_7
a_{11}	$m-a_{11}$	a_1	$m-a_1$	a_3	$m-a_3$	$m-a_4+a_1-a_{10}$	$a_4-a_1+a_{10}$
$a_9+a_{10}-a_6+a_8+a_7-m$	$a_6-a_8+2*m-a_7-a_9-a_{10}$	$m-a_2$	a_2	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	$a_{10}-a_9+a_7-a_1-a_5+a_4+a_{11}$	$m+a_9-a_7+a_1+a_5-a_4-a_{11}-a_{10}$
$a_6+a_4-a_8-a_1+m-a_9$	$a_9-a_6-a_4+a_8+a_1$	$m-a_3$	a_3	$m-a_1$	a_1	$a_9+a_5-a_{11}$	$m-a_9-a_5+a_{11}$
$a_9+a_3-a_{11}$	$a_{10}+a_2+a_4+a_8+a_7-a_1+a_{11}-2*m$	$2*m-a_9-a_{10}-a_8$	a_{10}	a_9	a_8	$3*m-a_9-a_{10}-a_2-a_3-a_8-a_7+a_1$	$m-a_4$
$m-a_9-a_3+a_{11}$	$3*m-a_{10}-a_2-a_4-a_8-a_7+a_1-a_{11}$	$a_9+a_{10}+a_8-m$	$m-a_{10}$	$m-a_9$	$m-a_8$	$a_9+a_{10}+a_2+a_3+a_8+a_7-a_1-2*m$	a_4

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal flat-type striped** magic square of order 8 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order embedded with a magic square of order 4. This magic square of order 4 is composed of two equal sums 2×8 . The internal two strips are forming **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, where m is the width of the **strip** See below an example:

Example 2.6. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 8 based on Result 2.6:

	pan	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172
172	68	20	23	-4	26	41	32	-34	172
172	-25	23	20	47	17	2	11	77	172
172	-31	74	20	23	14	29	14	29	172
172	41	2	11	32	17	26	-4	47	172
172	65	-22	29	14	23	20	59	-16	172
172	11	32	26	17	32	11	17	26	172
172	11	77	-19	38	35	32	-25	23	172
	32	-34	62	5	8	11	68	20	172
	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172

It is a **pandiagonal flat-type striped** magic square of order 8 with magic sum $S_{8 \times 8} := 172$. The magic sums of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 is given as $S_{4 \times 4} := 86$. See below the details:

	pan	86	86	86	86
86	20	23	14	29	86
86	11	32	17	26	86
86	29	14	23	20	86
	26	17	32	11	86
	86	86	86	86	86

2.3.3 Corner-Type

Result 2.7. An **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 8 in **cyclic way** is given by

$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	a_4	$m-a_4$	$m-a_6$	a_6
$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	a_2	a_3	$(1/2)*m+a_2-a_5$	$(1/2)*m-a_2+a_5$	$a_1+a_7-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7$
a_2	a_3	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	$(1/2)*m-a_3-a_2+a_1+a_5$	$a_3+a_2+(1/2)*m-a_1-a_5$	$(1/2)*m+a_1-a_3-a_2+a_8$	$a_3+a_2+(1/2)*m-a_8-a_1$
$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_4-a_1+a_3$	$a_4+a_1-a_3$	$m-a_1+a_3-a_4+a_5-a_8$	$a_1-a_3+a_4-a_5+a_8$
$(1/2)*m-a_4-a_1+a_3+a_2$	$a_1-a_2+a_5$	$m-a_5$	$a_4+(1/2)*m-a_3$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7+a_2-a_5$	$a_1+a_7-a_2+a_5-(1/2)*m$
$a_4+(1/2)*m+a_1-a_3-a_2$	$(m-a_1+a_2-a_5)$	a_5	$(1/2)*m+a_3-a_4$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$a_6+a_4-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_4-a_6$
$a_6+a_3+a_2-a_1-(1/2)*m$	$m-a_7$	$m-a_8$	$(1/2)*m-a_3+a_4-a_5+a_8$	$a_1+a_7-a_2+a_5-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_4-a_6$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$
$(3/2)*m+a_1-a_6-a_3-a_2$	a_7	a_8	$(1/2)*m+a_3-a_4+a_5-a_8$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7+a_2-a_5$	$a_6+a_4-(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal corner-type striped** magic square of order 8 composed of different size magic rectangles, where the width is always 2. In the upper-left corner there are two **pandiagonal** magic squares of orders 4 and 6 composed of equal width magic rectangles. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, where **m** is the width of the **strip** See below an example:

Example 2.7. Below is a example of **pandiagonal corner-type striped** magic square of order 8 based on Result 2.7:

	pan	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184
184	19	10	33	30	19	27	21	25	184
184	27	36	13	16	14	32	15	31	184
184	13	16	27	36	26	20	35	11	184
184	33	30	19	10	33	13	24	22	184
184	23	19	24	26	23	23	22	24	184
184	23	27	22	20	23	23	21	25	184
184	21	18	15	35	24	25	23	23	184
	25	28	31	11	22	21	23	23	184
	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184

It is a **pandiagonal corner-type striped** magic square of order 8 with magic sum $S_{8 \times 8} := 184$. The magic sums of **pandiagonal** magic squares of orders 6 and 4 are given as $S_{6 \times 6} := 138$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 92$. See below the details:

	pan	138	138	138	138	138	138
138	19	10	33	30	19	27	138
138	27	36	13	16	14	32	138
138	13	16	27	36	26	20	138
138	33	30	19	10	33	13	138
138	23	19	24	26	23	23	138
	23	27	22	20	23	23	138
	138	138	138	138	138	138	138

	pan	92	92	92	92
92	19	10	33	30	92
92	27	36	13	16	92
92	13	16	27	36	92
	33	30	19	10	92
	92	92	92	92	92

2.4 Algebraic Pandiagonal Striped Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 10, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.4.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.8. An *algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type striped* magic square of order 10 is given by

a_{13}	$m-a_{13}$	$a_3-a_4+a_{24}+a_{28}+a_{31}+a_5-a_1+(49/2)*m$	$a_2+a_3+a_4-a_6-a_{26}-26*m+a_1$	$a_{26}+a_{29}-a_1+(1/2)*m-a_{37}$	$a_1-11*m-a_2-a_3-a_{36}-a_{24}-a_{31}-a_5$	$a_2+a_{36}+a_4+a_{13}+a_3-2+a_{31}-(5/2)*m$	$a_{37}-a_4+a_6-a_{13}+(35/2)*m-a_{32}-a_{29}-a_{28}-a_{31}-a_2-a_3$	$12*m$	$(-11*m)$
$m-a_{13}$	a_{13}	$a_4-a_{24}-a_{28}-a_{31}-a_5+a_1-(47/2)*m-a_3$	$a_6-a_{13}+a_{26}+a_{13}-a_1+27*m-a_2-a_3-a_4$	$a_{37}-a_{26}-a_{29}+a_1+(1/2)*m$	$a_3+a_{36}+12*m+a_2+a_{24}+a_{31}+a_5-a_1$	$(7/2)*m-a_{36}-a_4-a_{13}-a_2-a_{32}-a_{31}$	$a_2+a_3-a_{37}+a_4-a_6+a_{13}-(33/2)*m+a_{32}+a_{29}+a_{28}+a_{31}$	$(-11*m)$	$12*m$
$a_4-a_{28}+a_1-(51/2)*m$	$a_{28}-a_1+(53/2)*m-a_4$	a_1	$m-a_1$	a_5	a_6	$a_4-(27/2)*m+a_1-a_5-a_6$	$(31/2)*m-a_4-a_1$	$a_{25}+a_{26}-a_5+a_1-a_2-(23/2)*m-a_{13}-a_{32}-a_{28}-a_{31}-a_3$	$a_2+a_3+a_{13}-a_{25}-a_{26}+a_{28}+a_{32}+a_{31}+a_5-a_1+(25/2)*m$
$(53/2)*m-a_4+a_6-a_{13}-a_{29}+a_{13}+a_5-a_1$	$a_4-a_6+a_{29}-a_5+a_1-(51/2)*m$	a_2	$m-a_2$	$m-a_5$	$m-a_6$	$(29/2)*m-a_1+a_5+a_6-a_4$	$a_4-(29/2)*m+a_1$	$a_2+a_{13}+a_{32}-m$	$2*m-a_2-a_{13}-a_{32}$
a_{37}	$m-a_{37}$	a_3	$m-a_3$	$a_5+a_2+a_3-m$	a_1-14*m	$(1/2)*m+a_4-a_5$	$(33/2)*m-a_2-a_3-a_4-a_1$	$m-a_{24}$	a_{24}
a_{36}	$m-a_{36}$	$(-13*m-a_6)$	$14*m+a_6$	$2*m-a_2-a_3-a_5$	$15*m-a_1$	$(1/2)*m-a_4+a_5$	$a_2+a_3-(31/2)*m+a_4+a_1$	$m-a_{25}$	a_{25}
$4*m-a_2-a_{32}-a_{31}-a_3-a_5-a_{36}-a_4$	$a_{36}+a_4-3*m+a_2+a_{32}+a_{31}+a_3+a_5$	$16*m-a_1-a_2-a_3+a_6-a_4$	$a_1+a_2+a_3-15*m-a_6+a_4$	$m-a_4+a_5-a_1$	$a_4+a_1-15*m+a_3$	$(3/2)*m-a_5-a_3$	$(29/2)*m$	$m-a_{26}$	a_{26}
$a_2+a_3-a_{37}+a_4-a_6-2*m+a_{32}+a_{29}+a_{28}+a_{31}$	$a_{37}-a_4+a_6+3*m-a_{32}-a_{29}-a_{28}-a_{31}-a_2-a_3$	a_4	$m-a_4$	$a_4-a_5+a_1$	$16*m-a_4-a_1-a_3$	$a_5-(1/2)*m+a_3$	$(-27/2)*m$	$a_3+a_{24}+a_{28}+a_{31}+a_5-a_1+(25/2)*m$	$a_1-(23/2)*m-a_3-a_{24}-a_{28}-a_{31}-a_5$
$(-11*m)$	$12*m$	$a_2+(25/2)*m+a_{32}+a_{28}+a_{31}+a_3-a_{25}-a_{26}+a_5$	$m-a_{32}$	$m-a_{31}$	$a_{25}+a_{26}+a_{29}-a_5-(27/2)*m-a_2-a_3$	$m-a_{29}$	$m-a_{28}$	$m-a_{13}$	a_{13}
$12*m$	$(-11*m)$	$a_{25}+a_{26}-a_5-a_2-(23/2)*m-a_{32}-a_{28}-a_{31}-a_3$	a_{32}	a_{31}	$(29/2)*m+a_2+a_3-a_{25}-a_{26}-a_{29}+a_5$	a_{29}	a_{28}	a_{13}	$m-a_{13}$

• Details

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type striped* magic square of order 10 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 embedded with a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6. It is again composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and one of order 2×6 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$ and $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, where m is the width of the *strip*. See below an example:

Example 2.8. Below is an example of a *pandiagonal cyclic-type striped* magic square of order 10 based on Result 2.8:

	pan	460	460	460	460	460	460	460	460	460	460
460	39	53	2413	-2374	61	-1237	43	1370	1104	-1012	460
460	53	39	-2321	2466	31	1329	49	-1278	-1012	1104	460
460	-2346	2438	21	71	33	36	-1260	1375	-1235	1327	460
460	2402	-2310	24	68	59	56	1352	-1283	31	61	460
460	66	26	27	65	-8	-1267	43	1416	50	42	460
460	63	29	-1232	1324	100	1359	49	-1324	47	45	460
460	74	18	1406	-1314	74	-1302	78	1334	44	48	460
460	17	75	30	62	18	1394	14	-1242	1339	-1247	460
460	-1012	1104	1309	32	35	-1179	38	41	53	39	460
	1104	-1012	-1217	60	57	1271	54	51	39	53	460
	460	460	460	460	460	460	460	460	460	460	460

It is a **pandiagonal cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 10 with magic sum $S_{10 \times 10} := 460$. The magic sum of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 is given as $S_{6 \times 6} := 276$. The width of each magic rectangle is 92. See below the details:

	pan	276	276	276	276	276	276
276	21	71	33	36	-1260	1375	276
276	24	68	59	56	1352	-1283	276
276	27	65	-8	-1267	43	1416	276
276	-1232	1324	100	1359	49	-1324	276
276	1406	-1314	74	-1302	78	1334	276
	30	62	18	1394	14	-1242	276
	276	276	276	276	276	276	276

21	71	92	33	36	-1260	1375	184
24	68	92	59	56	1352	-1283	184
27	65	92	92	92	92	92	
-1232	1324	92	-8	-1267	43	1416	184
1406	-1314	92	100	1359	49	-1324	184
30	62	92	92	92	92	92	
276	276		74	-1302	78	1334	184
			18	1394	14	-1242	184
			92	92	92	92	

2.4.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.9. An *algebraic pandiagonal flat-type striped* magic square of order 10 in is given by

a_{10}	$m-a_{10}$	$a_8+a_3+a_{14}+a_{17}+a_{16}-a_{13}-a_6-a_1-(15/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m-a_{17}-a_{11}+a_2+a_1+a_4-a_9$	$7*m+a_9-a_{16}+a_{11}$	a_7	$a_{13}+2*m-a_3-a_2-a_7+a_{10}-a_4-a_8$	$a_6+m-a_{14}-a_{10}$	$7*m-a_3+a_5+a_{17}+a_{11}+a_6-a_2-a_1$	$a_3-a_5-a_{17}-a_{11}-a_6+a_2+a_1-6*m$
$m-a_{10}$	a_{10}	$a_{13}+a_6+a_1+(17/2)*m-a_8-a_3-a_{14}-a_{17}-a_{16}$	$a_9+a_{17}+a_{11}-a_2-a_4-a_1+(1/2)*m$	$a_{16}-a_{11}-6*m-a_9$	$m-a_7$	$a_8-a_{13}+a_3+a_2+a_7-a_{10}+a_4-m$	$a_{14}+a_{10}-a_6$	$a_3-a_5-a_{17}-a_{11}-a_6+a_2+a_1-6*m$	$7*m-a_3+a_5+a_{17}+a_{11}+a_6-a_2-a_1$
$(7/2)*m-a_{17}-a_{16}-a_{15}-a_8+a_{13}-a_3-a_7-a_{14}$	$a_{17}+a_{16}+a_{15}+a_8-a_{13}-(5/2)*m+a_3+a_7+a_{14}$	$-(13/2)*m$	a_1	a_2	$(3/2)*m-a_6-a_5$	$8*m-a_1-a_2+a_6+a_5-a_3$	a_3	$a_5-a_{14}-a_{16}-a_{10}-a_{12}+2*a_6+a_4+8*m-a_3$	$a_3-a_5+a_{14}+a_{16}+a_{10}+a_{12}-2*a_6-a_4-7*m$
a_{17}	$m-a_{17}$	$(15/2)*m$	$m-a_1$	$m-a_2$	$a_6+a_5-(1/2)*m$	$a_1+a_2-a_6-a_5+a_3-7*m$	$m-a_3$	$a_{10}+a_{13}+a_1-m$	$2*m-a_{10}-a_{13}-a_1$
a_{16}	$m-a_{16}$	a_4	$m-a_4$	$a_4+a_1+a_2-m$	$2*m-a_1-a_2-a_4$	$m-a_3+a_4-(-13/2)*m$	$a_3-a_4+(-13/2)*m$	$m-a_8$	a_8
a_{15}	$m-a_{15}$	a_5	$m-a_5$	$(-6*m-a_6)$	$7*m+a_6$	$a_3-7*m-a_6+a_2$	$8*m-a_3+a_6-a_2$	$a_9+a_{12}+m+a_{11}-a_6-a_2-a_1-a_4$	$a_6+a_2+a_4+a_1-a_9-a_{12}-a_{11}$
$a_8-a_{13}-(1/2)*m+a_3+a_7$	$(3/2)*m-a_8+a_{13}-a_3-a_7$	$a_3-(11/2)*m-a_6-a_4-a_5$	$a_6+(13/2)*m+a_4+a_5-a_3$	$(1/2)*m+a_3-a_4$	$(1/2)*m-a_3+a_4$	$(3/2)*m-a_4-a_2$	$a_4-(1/2)*m+a_2$	$m-a_9$	a_9
a_{14}	$m-a_{14}$	$(15/2)*m-a_3+a_6$	$a_3-a_6-(13/2)*m$	$(17/2)*m+a_6-a_1-a_2-a_3$	$a_1+a_2-(15/2)*m+a_3-a_6$	a_6	$m-a_6$	$a_8+a_3-a_5+a_{14}+a_{16}-a_{11}-a_{13}-a_6+a_2-7*m$	$a_5-a_{14}-a_{16}+a_{11}+a_{13}+a_6-a_2+8*m-a_8-a_3$
$a_3-a_5-a_{17}-a_{11}-a_6+a_2+a_1-6*m$	$7*m-a_3+a_5+a_{17}+a_{11}+a_6-a_2-a_1$	$a_3-a_5+a_{14}+a_{16}+a_{12}-2*a_6-a_4-(27/2)*m$	$m-a_{13}$	$a_8+a_{15}+a_6+a_2+a_4+a_7+a_1+4*m$	$m-a_{12}$	$m-a_{11}$	$a_5-a_{14}-a_{16}-a_{15}+a_{11}+a_{13}+a_6-a_2-a_7-a_1+(19/2)*m-a_8-a_3$	$m-a_{10}$	a_{10}
$7*m-a_3+a_5+a_{17}+a_{11}+a_6-a_2-a_1$	$a_3-a_5-a_{17}-a_{11}-a_6+a_2+a_1-6*m$	$a_5-a_{14}-a_{16}-a_{12}+(29/2)*m+2*a_6+a_4-a_3$	a_{13}	$(-a_8-a_{15}-a_6-a_2-a_4-a_7-a_1-3*m)$	a_{12}	a_{11}	$a_8+a_3-a_5+a_{14}+a_{16}+a_{15}-a_{11}-a_{13}-a_6+a_2+a_7+a_1-(17/2)*m$	a_{10}	$m-a_{10}$

• Details

It is a *pandiagonal flat-type striped* magic square of order 10 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×10 and two magic rectangles of order 2×6 embedded with a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6. It is again composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and one magic rectangle of order 2×6 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$ and $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, where m is the width of the *strip*. See below an example:

Example 2.9. Below is an example of a *pandiagonal flat-type striped* magic square of order 10 based on Result 2.9:

	pan	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510
510	48	54	-615	-39	744	39	147	30	831	-729	510
510	54	48	717	141	-642	63	-45	72	-729	831	510
510	48	54	-663	21	24	84	813	27	696	-594	510
510	69	33	765	81	78	18	-711	75	24	78	510
510	66	36	30	72	-27	129	768	-666	60	42	510
510	63	39	33	69	-648	750	-699	801	141	-39	510
510	0	102	-633	735	48	54	99	3	57	45	510
510	60	42	774	-672	831	-729	36	66	-672	774	510
510	-729	831	-1305	45	663	48	51	804	54	48	510
	831	-729	1407	57	-561	54	51	-702	48	54	510
	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510

It is a **pandiagonal flat-type striped** magic square of order 10 with magic sum $S_{10 \times 10} := 510$. The magic sum of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 is given as $S_{6 \times 6} := 306$. The width of each magic rectangle is 102. See below some details:

	pan	306	306	306	306	306	306	306
306	-663	21	24	84	813	27	306	
306	765	81	78	18	-711	75	306	
306	30	72	-27	129	768	-666	306	
306	33	69	-648	750	-699	801	306	
306	-633	735	48	54	99	3	306	
	774	-672	831	-729	36	66	306	
	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	

		-663	21	24	84	813	27	306		
		765	81	78	18	-711	75	306		
		102	102	102	102	102	102			
		30	72	102	-27	129	102	768	-666	102
		33	69	102	-648	750	102	-699	801	102
		-633	735	102	48	54	102	99	3	102
		774	-672	102	831	-729	102	36	66	102
		204	204		204	204		204	204	

2.4.3 Corner-Type

Result 2.10. An *algebraic pandiagonal corner-type striped* magic square of order 10 is given by

$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	a_4	$m-a_4$	$m-a_6$	a_6	$m-a_9$	a_9
$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	a_2	a_3	$(1/2)*m+a_2-a_5$	$(1/2)*m-a_2+a_5$	$a_1+a_7-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7$	$a_1+a_{10}+a_7-m$	$2*m-a_1-a_{10}-a_7$
a_2	a_3	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	$(1/2)*m-a_3-a_2+a_1+a_5$	$a_3+a_2+(1/2)*m-a_1-a_5$	$(1/2)*m+a_1-a_3-a_2+a_8$	$a_3+a_2+(1/2)*m-a_8-a_1$	$a_6-a_{12}+a_8-a_2-a_3+a_4+a_1$	$m-a_6+a_{12}-a_8+a_2+a_3-a_4-a_1$
$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_4-a_1+a_3$	$a_4+a_1-a_3$	$m-a_1+a_3-a_4+a_5-a_8$	$a_1-a_3+a_4-a_5+a_8$	$(1/2)*m-a_1+a_{11}$	$(1/2)*m+a_1-a_{11}$
$(1/2)*m-a_4-a_1+a_3+a_2$	$a_1-a_2+a_5$	$m-a_5$	$a_4+(1/2)*m-a_3$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7+a_2-a_5$	$a_1+a_7-a_2+a_5-(1/2)*m$	$2*m-a_8+a_2+a_3-a_4-a_{11}-a_1-a_7$	$a_8-a_2-a_3+a_4+a_{11}+a_1+a_7-m$
$a_4+(1/2)*m+a_1-a_3-a_2$	$m-a_1+a_2-a_5$	a_5	$(1/2)*m+a_3-a_4$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$a_6+a_4-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_4-a_6$	a_{12}	$m-a_{12}$
$a_6+a_3+a_2-a_1-(1/2)*m$	$m-a_7$	$m-a_8$	$(1/2)*m-a_3+a_4-a_5+a_8$	$a_1+a_7-a_2+a_5-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_4-a_6$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$m-a_{10}$	a_{10}
$(3/2)*m+a_1-a_6-a_3-a_2$	a_7	a_8	$(1/2)*m+a_3-a_4+a_5-a_8$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7+a_2-a_5$	$a_6+a_4-(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m-a_6+a_9$	$(1/2)*m+a_6-a_9$
$a_2+a_3-a_1+a_9-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_{10}-a_7$	$(3/2)*m-a_6+a_{12}-a_8-a_4$	$m-a_{11}$	$a_8-a_2-a_3+a_4+a_{11}+a_1+a_7-m$	$m-a_{12}$	a_{10}	$(1/2)*m+a_6-a_9$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$
$a_1+(3/2)*m-a_9-a_2-a_3$	$a_{10}+a_7-(1/2)*m$	$a_6-a_{12}+a_8+a_4-(1/2)*m$	a_{11}	$2*m-a_8+a_2+a_3-a_4-a_{11}-a_1-a_7$	a_{12}	$m-a_{10}$	$(1/2)*m-a_6+a_9$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$

• Details

Details It is an *algebraic pandiagonal corner-type striped* magic square of order 10, where the magic squares of order 4, 6 and 8 are at the upper-left corner. These are also *pandiagonals* magic squares. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$ and $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, where m is the width of the *strip*. See below an example:

Example 2.10. Below is an example of a *pandiagonal corner-type striped* magic square of order 10 based on Result 2.10:

	pan	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	
210		13	10	31	30	13	29	27	15	24	18	210
210		29	32	11	12	18	24	5	37	3	39	210
210		11	12	29	32	22	20	25	17	11	31	210
210		31	30	13	10	31	11	28	14	31	11	210
210		21	13	28	22	21	21	34	8	31	11	210
210		21	29	14	20	21	21	7	35	21	21	210
210		7	26	25	25	8	35	21	21	23	19	210
210		35	16	17	17	34	7	21	21	24	18	210
210		10	28	39	22	11	21	19	18	21	21	210
		32	14	3	20	31	21	23	24	21	21	210
		210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

It is a **pandiagonal corner-type striped** magic square of order 10 with magic sum $S_{10 \times 10} := 210$. The magic sum of **pandiagonal** magic squares of orders 8, 6 and 4 are $S_{8 \times 8} := 168$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 126$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 84$. The width of each magic rectangle is 42. See below some details:

	pan	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168
168		13	10	31	30	13	29	27	15	168
168		29	32	11	12	18	24	5	37	168
168		11	12	29	32	22	20	25	17	168
168		31	30	13	10	31	11	28	14	168
168		21	13	28	22	21	21	34	8	168
168		21	29	14	20	21	21	7	35	168
168		7	26	25	25	8	35	21	21	168
		35	16	17	17	34	7	21	21	168
		168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

	pan	126	126	126	126	126	126
126	13	10	31	30	13	29	126
126	29	32	11	12	18	24	126
126	11	12	29	32	22	20	126
126	31	30	13	10	31	11	126
126	21	13	28	22	21	21	126
	21	29	14	20	21	21	126
	126	126	126	126	126	126	126

	pan	84	84	84	84
84	13	10	31	30	84
84	29	32	11	12	84
84	11	12	29	32	84
	31	30	13	10	84
	84	84	84	84	84

2.5 Algebraic Pandiagonal Striped Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 12, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.5.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.11. An *algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type striped* magic square of order 12 is given by

a7	$2^2a^9+a^7-a^{10}-a^8-a^{11}+2^2a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}+a^2+a^3-12^2m$	$2^2a^{10}+a^8+a^{20}+a^{23}+a^{22}+a^{21}+a^{11}+a^{19}-2^2a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}+a^{14}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}-2^2a^2-2^2a^3+85^2m-2^2a^9-2^2a^7$	$9^2m-a^9-a^7-a^{23}-a^{18}-a^{14}-a^{12}$	$a^{11}+a^{16}-a^{22}$	$a^7-a^7+a^{10}+a^8-a^{21}-a^{17}+a^{15}$	$a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}+3^2a^{13}+a^2+a^3-72^2m-2^2a^{10}-2^2a^8-a^{11}$	a8	$a^7-a^{20}-5^2m$	$a^7+a^9-a^7-a^{19}+a^{18}$	$2^2a^9+2^2a^7-a^{10}-a^8-a^{11}+2^2a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}+a^2+a^3+(20/3)^2m$	$a^{10}+a^8+a^{11}-2^2a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}-a^2-a^3-(17/3)^2m-2^2a^9-2^2a^7$
m-a7	$a^{10}+a^8+a^{11}-2^2a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}-a^2-a^3+13^2m-2^2a^9-a^7$	$10^2a^7+2^2a^9-8^2a^7-2^2a^{10}-a^8-a^{20}-a^{23}-a^{22}-a^{21}-a^{11}-a^{19}+2^2a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}-a^{14}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}+2^2a^2+2^2a^3-84^2m$	$a^9+a^7+a^{23}+a^{18}+a^{14}+a^{12}-8^2m$	$a^{22}-a^{11}-a^{16}+m$	$a^{21}+a^{17}-a^{15}+m-a^{10}-a^8$	$2^2a^{10}+2^2a^8+a^{11}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}-3^2a^{13}-a^2-a^3+73^2m$	m-a8	$6^2m-a^7+a^{20}$	$(-a^7-a^9+a^7+a^{19}-a^{18}+m)$	$(-56/3)^2m$	$(59/3)^2m$
$9^2m-a^9-a^7-a^{23}-a^{18}-a^{14}-a^{13}$	$a^9+a^7+a^{23}+a^{18}+a^{14}+a^{13}-8^2m$	6^2m	$a^9+a^7-a^{10}-a^8-a^{11}+a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}+a^2+a^3-11^2m$	a4	$a^6-a^9-a^7+a^{23}-a^{18}-a^{17}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}+a^3-(260/3)^2m$	a5	$a^{10}+a^8-a^{23}+a^{11}-a^5+a^{16}+a^{15}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}-a^2-2^2a^3+(284/3)^2m-a^6-a^4$	$a^9+a^7-a^{10}-a^8-a^{23}-a^{11}+a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}-a^{14}+a^2+a^3+(44/3)^2m$	$a^{10}+a^8+a^{23}+a^{11}-a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}+a^{14}-a^2-a^3-(41/3)^2m-a^9-a^7$	$a^9+a^{10}+a^8-a^{20}-a^{22}-a^{21}+a^{11}-a^{19}-a^{17}+m$	$a^{20}+a^{22}+a^{21}-a^{11}+a^{19}+a^{17}-a^9-a^{10}-a^8$
a23	m-a23	(-5^2m)	$a^{10}+a^8+a^{11}-a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}-a^2-a^3+12^2m-a^9-a^7$	m-a4	$a^9+a^7-a^{23}+a^{18}+a^{17}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}-a^3+(263/3)^2m-a^6$	m-a5	$a^6+a^4-a^{10}-a^8+a^{23}-a^{11}+a^5-a^{16}-a^{15}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}+a^2+2^2a^3-(281/3)^2m$	$a^{23}+a^{14}-(59/3)^2m$	$(62/3)^2m-a^{23}-a^{14}$	m-a9	a9
a22	m-a22	$a^{10}+a^8+a^{11}+a^{16}+a^{15}+a^{14}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}-a^2-a^3+73^2m-a^4$	$a^4-a^{10}-a^8-a^{11}-a^{16}-a^{15}-a^{14}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}+a^2+a^3-72^2m$	$a^3+a^2-a^1$	a1	m-a2	m-a3	$(-a^6-6^2a^7+6^2a^7-a^4+a^4+2^2a^{10}+2^2a^8-a^{20}-a^{23}-a^{21}+2^2a^{11}-a^5-a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+2^2a^{15}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}-a^2-2^2a^3+(284/3)^2m)$	$a^6+6^2a^7-6^2a^7+a^4-2^2a^{10}-2^2a^8+a^{20}+a^{23}+a^{21}-2^2a^{11}+a^5+a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}+a^2+2^2a^3-(281/3)^2m$	m-a10	a10
a21	m-a21	$a^2+(62/3)^2m-a^6-a^23-a^{14}$	$a^6+a^{23}+a^{14}-a^2-(59/3)^2m$	$a^1-a^3-a^2+m$	m-a1	a2	a3	$(-2^2a^7-a^9+a^7+a^{20}+a^{21}+a^5+a^{16}+5^2m)$	$2^2a^7+a^9-a^7-a^{20}-a^{21}-a^5-a^{16}-4^2m$	$3^2a^{13}+a^2+a^3-75^2m$	$76^2m-3^2a^{13}-a^2-a^3$
$a^7-a^7+a^{10}+a^8-a^{17}$	$a^{17}+m-a^{10}-a^8$	$7^2m-a^2-a^3-a^5+a^1$	$a^2+a^3+a^5-a^1-6^2m$	a2	a3	$a^1-a^3-a^2+m$	m-a1	$a^6-a^{10}-a^8-a^{11}-a^{16}-a^{15}-a^{14}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}+a^2+a^3-72^2m$	$(-a^6+a^{10}+a^8+a^{11}+a^{16}+a^{15}+a^{14}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}-a^2-a^3+73^2m)$	m-a11	a11
$3^2a^7+3^2a^9-2^2a^{10}-2^2a^8-a^{20}-a^{22}-a^{21}-a^{11}-a^{19}+3^2a^{18}+2^2a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}+a^{14}+a^{13}+a^2+a^3-18^2m$	$19^2m-3^2a^7-3^2a^9+2^2a^{10}+2^2a^8+a^{20}+a^{22}+a^{21}+a^{11}+a^{19}-3^2a^{18}-2^2a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}-a^{14}-a^{13}-a^2-a^3$	$a^6+a^9+a^7+a^4-2^2a^{10}-2^2a^8+a^{23}-2^2a^{11}+a^5+a^{18}+a^{17}-2^2a^{16}-2^2a^{15}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}-a^1+2^2a^2+3^2a^3-(314/3)^2m$	$2^2a^{10}+2^2a^8-a^{23}+2^2a^{11}-a^5-a^{18}-a^{17}+2^2a^{16}+2^2a^{15}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}+a^1-2^2a^2-3^2a^3+(317/3)^2m-a^6-a^9-a^7-a^4$	m-a2	m-a3	$a^3+a^2-a^1$	a1	$a^7-a^7+a^4+a^{23}+a^{14}-a^2-(59/3)^2m$	$(-a^4-a^{23}-a^{14}+a^2+(62/3)^2m)$	$a^{17}+m-a^{10}-a^8$	$a^{10}+a^8-a^{17}$
a20	m-a20	$a^{10}+a^8+a^{23}+a^{11}-a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}+a^{14}-a^2-a^3-(41/3)^2m-a^9-a^7$	$a^9+a^7-a^{10}-a^8-a^{23}-a^{11}+a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}-a^{14}+a^2+a^3+(44/3)^2m$	$a^6+6^2a^7-6^2a^7+a^4-2^2a^{10}-2^2a^8+a^{20}+a^{23}+a^{21}-2^2a^{11}+a^5+a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-2^2a^{15}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}-a^1+2^2a^2+3^2a^3-(299/3)^2m$	$a^{10}+a^8-a^{20}-a^{21}+a^{11}-a^5-a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{15}+a^1-a^2-a^3+7^2m$	m-a6	$a^9+a^7-a^4-a^{23}+a^{18}+a^{17}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}-a^3+(263/3)^2m$	(-5^2m)	$(-a^9-a^7+a^{10}+a^8+a^{11}-a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}-a^2-a^3+12^2m)$	m-a12	a12
a19	m-a19	$(62/3)^2m-a^{23}-a^{14}$	$a^{23}+a^{14}-(59/3)^2m$	$2^2a^{10}+2^2a^8-a^{20}-a^{23}-a^{21}+2^2a^{11}-a^5-a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+2^2a^{15}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}+a^1-2^2a^2-3^2a^3+(302/3)^2m-a^6-a^4$	$(-a^{10}-a^8+a^{20}+a^{21}-a^{11}+a^5+a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{15}-a^1+a^2+a^3-6^2m)$	a6	$(-a^9-a^7+a^4+a^{23}-a^{18}-a^{17}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}+a^3-(260/3)^2m)$	6^2m	$a^9+a^7-a^{10}-a^8-a^{11}+a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}+a^2+a^3-11^2m$	$2^2a^{10}+a^8+a^{20}+a^{22}+a^{21}+a^{11}+a^{19}-2^2a^{18}-a^{20}-a^{22}-a^{21}-a^{11}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}+a^{12}-3^2a^{13}-2^2a^2-2^2a^3+86^2m-2^2a^7-2^2a^9$	$2^2a^9+2^2a^7-2^2a^{10}-a^8-a^{20}-a^{22}-a^{21}-a^{11}-a^{19}+2^2a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}-a^{12}+3^2a^{13}+2^2a^2+2^2a^3-85^2m$
$a^{10}+a^8+a^{11}-2^2a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}-a^2-a^3-(17/3)^2m-2^2a^9-2^2a^7$	$2^2a^9+2^2a^7-a^{10}-a^8-a^{11}+2^2a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}+a^2+a^3+(20/3)^2m$	$a^{20}+a^{22}+a^{21}-a^{11}+a^{19}+a^{17}+6^2m-a^9-a^7-a^{10}-a^8$	m-a18	$3^2a^7+3^2a^9-a^{20}-a^{22}-a^{21}-a^{19}+3^2a^{18}+a^{17}+a^{14}+a^{13}+a^2+a^3-21^2m$	m-a17	m-a16	m-a15	m-a14	m-a13	m-a7	$a^{10}+a^8+a^{11}-2^2a^{18}-a^{17}+a^{16}+a^{15}-a^2-a^3+13^2m-a^7-2^2a^9$
$2^2a^7+(59/3)^2m-2^2a^7$	$(-56/3)^2m$	$a^9+a^7+a^{10}+a^8-a^{20}-a^{22}-a^{21}+a^{11}-a^{19}-a^{17}-5^2m$	a18	$a^{20}+a^{22}+a^{21}+a^{19}-3^2a^{18}-a^{17}-a^{14}-a^{13}-a^2-a^3+22^2m-3^2a^7-3^2a^9$	a17	a16	a15	a14	a13	a7	$2^2a^9+a^7-a^{10}-a^8-a^{11}+2^2a^{18}+a^{17}-a^{16}-a^{15}+a^2+a^3-12^2m$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 12 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×10 embedded with a **algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 8. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, where **m** is the width of the **strip**. See below an example:

Example 2.11. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 12 based on Result 2.11:

12	pan	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360
360	7	-697	5167	457	5	-5	-4337	8	-313	8	430	-370	360
360	53	757	-5107	-397	55	65	4397	52	373	52	-1120	1180	360
360	456	-396	360	-664	4	-5192	5	5667	839	-779	-1	61	360
360	23	37	-300	724	56	5252	55	-5607	-1143	1203	51	9	360
360	22	38	4418	-4358	4	1	58	57	5635	-5575	50	10	360
360	21	39	1199	-1139	56	59	2	3	346	-286	-4456	4516	360
360	1	59	411	-351	2	3	56	59	-4356	4416	49	11	360
360	-1072	1132	-6272	6332	58	57	4	1	-1141	1201	59	1	360
360	20	40	-779	839	-5931	379	54	5254	-300	724	48	12	360
360	19	41	1203	-1143	5991	-319	6	-5194	360	-664	5190	-5130	360
360	-370	430	414	42	-1191	43	44	45	46	47	53	757	360
	1180	-1120	-354	18	1251	17	16	15	14	13	7	-697	360
	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360

It is a **pandiagonal cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 12 with magic sum $S_{12 \times 12} := 360$. The magic sum of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 is given as $S_{8 \times 8} := 240$ and the magic sum of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 is $S_{4 \times 4} := 120$. The width of each magic rectangle is 60. See below the details:

	pan	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240
240	360	-664	4	-5192	5	5667	839	-779	240	
240	-300	724	56	5252	55	-5607	-1143	1203	240	
240	4418	-4358	4	1	58	57	5635	-5575	240	
240	1199	-1139	56	59	2	3	346	-286	240	
240	411	-351	2	3	56	59	-4356	4416	240	
240	-6272	6332	58	57	4	1	-1141	1201	240	
240	-779	839	-5931	379	54	5254	-300	724	240	
	1203	-1143	5991	-319	6	-5194	360	-664	240	
	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	

	pan	120	120	120	120
120	4	1	58	57	120
120	56	59	2	3	120
120	2	3	56	59	120
	58	57	4	1	120
	120	120	120	120	120

2.5.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.12. An *algebraic pandiagonal flat-type striped* magic square of order 12 in **cyclic way** is given by

a10	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+2^*a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6-2^*a_2+a_{10}-2^*a_7+2^*a_9-a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5$	$a_{17}-5^*a_{21}-11^*a_{18}-(25/2)^*a_{20}-(19/2)^*a_{13}-11^*a_{19}-(19/2)^*a_{15}-(17/2)^*a_{14}+19^*a_6-13^*a_{16}-(25/2)^*m+a_{36}+(19/2)^*a_2-18^*a_1-(19/2)^*a_{10}-a_8+18^*a_7-(19/2)^*a_9+(19/2)^*a_3+18^*a_4+19^*a_5$	$(-)$ $a_{17}+5^*a_{21}+5^*a_{18}+(9/2)^*a_{20}+(7/2)^*a_{13}+5^*a_{19}+(7/2)^*a_{15}+(7/2)^*a_{14}+11^*a_6+5^*a_{16}-a_{12}+(15/2)^*m-(7/2)^*a_2+7^*a_1+(7/2)^*a_{10}-7^*a_7+(7/2)^*a_9-(7/2)^*a_3-7^*a_4-7^*a_5$	$(-a_{21}+a_{15}-2^*a_6-a_{39}+5^*m-a_2+2^*a_1+a_{10}-2^*a_7+a_9-a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5)$	$(-a_{18}-a_{20}-a_{13}-a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{14}+2^*a_6+a_{39}-m+a_2-2^*a_1-a_{10}+2^*a_7-a_9+a_3+2^*a_4+2^*a_5)$	$a_{17}+a_{21}+7^*a_{18}+9^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+6^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+6^*a_{14}-a_{11}-11^*a_6+9^*a_{16}+a_{12}+2^*m-5^*a_2+10^*a_1+5^*a_{10}+a_8-10^*a_7+5^*a_9-5^*a_3-10^*a_4-11^*a_5$	$a_{13}+a_{19}-a_{36}$	$3^*m-a_{17}-a_2+a_1-a_7-a_5-a_4-a_6-a_3+a_{10}$	$a_{15}-a_{16}+a_9$	$a_{17}-5^*a_{21}-5^*a_{18}-(9/2)^*a_{20}-(7/2)^*a_{13}-5^*a_{19}-(9/2)^*a_{15}-(7/2)^*a_{14}-a_{11}+7^*a_6-5^*a_{16}-(13/2)^*m+(9/2)^*a_2-8^*a_1-(9/2)^*a_{10}+a_8+8^*a_7-(9/2)^*a_9+(7/2)^*a_3+8^*a_4+8^*a_5$	$(-)$ $a_{17}+5^*a_{21}+4^*a_{18}+(9/2)^*a_{20}+(5/2)^*a_{13}+4^*a_{19}+(5/2)^*a_{15}+(5/2)^*a_{14}+a_{11}-5^*a_6+5^*a_{16}+(17/2)^*m-(7/2)^*a_2+6^*a_1+(5/2)^*a_{10}-a_8-6^*a_7+(5/2)^*a_9-(5/2)^*a_3-6^*a_4-6^*a_5$
m-a10	$(-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-2^*a_{15}-a_{14}+2^*a_6+m+a_2-2^*a_1-a_{10}+2^*a_7-2^*a_9+a_3+2^*a_4+2^*a_5)$	$(-)$ $a_{17}+5^*a_{21}+11^*a_{18}+(25/2)^*a_{20}+(19/2)^*a_{13}+11^*a_{19}+(19/2)^*a_{15}+(17/2)^*a_{14}-19^*a_6+13^*a_{16}+(27/2)^*m-a_{36}-(19/2)^*a_2+18^*a_1+(19/2)^*a_{10}+a_8-18^*a_7+(19/2)^*a_9-(19/2)^*a_3-18^*a_4-19^*a_5$	$a_{17}-5^*a_{21}-5^*a_{18}-(9/2)^*a_{20}-(7/2)^*a_{13}-5^*a_{19}-(7/2)^*a_{15}-(7/2)^*a_{14}-a_{11}+7^*a_6-5^*a_{16}+a_{12}-(13/2)^*m+(7/2)^*a_2-7^*a_1-(7/2)^*a_{10}+7^*a_7-(7/2)^*a_9+(7/2)^*a_3+7^*a_4+7^*a_5$	$a_{21}-a_{15}+2^*a_6+a_{39}-4^*m+a_2-2^*a_1-a_{10}+2^*a_7-a_9+a_3+2^*a_4+2^*a_5$	$a_{18}+a_{20}+a_{13}+a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6-a_{39}+2^*m-a_2+2^*a_1+a_{10}-2^*a_7+a_9+a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5$	$(-a_{17}-a_{21}-7^*a_{18}-9^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-6^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-6^*a_{14}+a_{11}+11^*a_6-9^*a_{16}-a_{12}-m+5^*a_2-10^*a_1-5^*a_{10}-a_8+10^*a_7-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+11^*a_5)$	$(-a_{13}-a_{19}+m+a_{36})$	$(-2^*m+a_{17}+a_2-a_1+a_7+a_5+a_4+a_6+a_3-a_{10})$	$(-a_{15}+a_{16}+m-a_9)$	$(-)$ $a_{17}+5^*a_{21}+5^*a_{18}+(9/2)^*a_{20}+(7/2)^*a_{13}+5^*a_{19}+(9/2)^*a_{15}+(7/2)^*a_{14}+a_{11}-7^*a_6+5^*a_{16}+(15/2)^*m-(9/2)^*a_2+8^*a_1+(9/2)^*a_{10}-a_8-8^*a_7+(9/2)^*a_9-(7/2)^*a_3-8^*a_4-8^*a_5$	$(-)$ $a_{17}-5^*a_{21}-4^*a_{18}-(9/2)^*a_{20}-(5/2)^*a_{13}-4^*a_{19}-(5/2)^*a_{15}-(5/2)^*a_{14}-a_{11}+5^*a_6-5^*a_{16}-(15/2)^*m+(7/2)^*a_2-6^*a_1-(5/2)^*a_{10}+a_8+6^*a_7-(5/2)^*a_9+(5/2)^*a_3+6^*a_4+6^*a_5$
$5^*a_{21}+5^*a_{18}+(9/2)^*a_{20}+(7/2)^*a_{13}+5^*a_{19}+(7/2)^*a_{15}+(7/2)^*a_{14}-4^*a_7+5^*a_{16}+(15/2)^*m-(7/2)^*a_2+7^*a_1+(7/2)^*a_{10}-7^*a_7+(7/2)^*a_9-(7/2)^*a_3-7^*a_4-7^*a_5-a_{17}$	$a_{17}-5^*a_{21}-5^*a_{18}-(9/2)^*a_{20}-(7/2)^*a_{13}-5^*a_{19}-(7/2)^*a_{15}-(7/2)^*a_{14}+7^*a_6-5^*a_{16}-(13/2)^*m+(7/2)^*a_2-7^*a_1-(7/2)^*a_{10}+7^*a_7-(7/2)^*a_9+(7/2)^*a_3+7^*a_4+7^*a_5$	$a_6+a_7+a_2+a_3+a_5+a_4-a_1-2^*m$	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6+m-a_2+2^*a_1+a_{10}-2^*a_7+a_9+a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5$	$10^*a_6-8^*a_{16}-5^*m+5^*a_2-10^*a_1-5^*a_{10}+10^*a_7-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+10^*a_5-5^*a_{18}-8^*a_{20}-5^*a_{13}-5^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}$	$(5^*a_{18}+8^*a_{20}+5^*a_{13}+5^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}-11^*a_6+8^*a_{16}+7^*m-5^*a_2+10^*a_1+5^*a_{10}-10^*a_7+5^*a_9-5^*a_3-10^*a_4-11^*a_5)$	$(-a_{17}-11^*a_{21}-11^*a_{18}-11^*a_{20}-7^*a_{13}-11^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-6^*a_{14}-a_{11}+13^*a_6-11^*a_{16}-3^*m+6^*a_2-12^*a_1-4^*a_{10}+12^*a_7-6^*a_9+6^*a_3+13^*a_4+13^*a_5)$	$a_{17}+11^*a_{21}+11^*a_{18}+11^*a_{20}+7^*a_{13}+11^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+6^*a_{14}+a_{11}-12^*a_6+11^*a_{16}+3^*m-6^*a_2+12^*a_1+4^*a_{10}-12^*a_7+6^*a_9-6^*a_3-13^*a_4-12^*a_5$	$m-a_6-a_3+a_8$	$(-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{14}+2^*a_6+m-a_2+a_1+a_{10}-a_7+a_9-a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5)$	$(-a_{17}-12^*a_{21}-10^*a_{18}-11^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-10^*a_{19}-3^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}-a_{11}+10^*a_6-12^*a_7+5^*a_2-10^*a_1-3^*a_{10}+10^*a_7-4^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+10^*a_5)$	$(a_{17}+12^*a_{21}+10^*a_{18}+11^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+10^*a_{19}+3^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}+a_{11}-1^*a_6+12^*a_7+m-5^*a_2+10^*a_1+3^*a_{10}-10^*a_7-4^*a_9-5^*a_3-10^*a_4-10^*a_5)$
$7^*a_6-6^*a_{16}-(7/2)^*m+(7/2)^*a_2-7^*a_1-(7/2)^*a_{10}+7^*a_7-(7/2)^*a_9+(7/2)^*a_3+7^*a_4+7^*a_5-6^*a_{21}-6^*a_{18}-(11/2)^*a_{20}-(7/2)^*a_{13}-6^*a_{19}-(7/2)^*a_{15}-(7/2)^*a_{14}$	$(7/2)^*a_9+(7/2)^*a_3+7^*a_4+7^*a_5$	$3^*m-a_6-a_7-a_2-a_3-a_5-a_4+a_1$	$2^*a_6+a_2-2^*a_1-a_{10}+2^*a_7-a_9+a_3+2^*a_4+2^*a_5-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{14}$	$5^*a_{18}+8^*a_{20}+5^*a_{13}+5^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}-10^*a_6+8^*a_{16}+6^*m-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+11^*a_5-8^*a_{20}-5^*a_{13}-5^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}$	$11^*a_6-8^*a_{16}-6^*m+5^*a_2-10^*a_1-5^*a_{10}+10^*a_7-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+11^*a_5-8^*a_{20}-5^*a_{13}-5^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}$	$a_{17}+11^*a_{21}+11^*a_{18}+11^*a_{20}+7^*a_{13}+11^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+6^*a_{14}+a_{11}-13^*a_6+11^*a_{16}+4^*m-6^*a_2+12^*a_1+4^*a_{10}-12^*a_7+6^*a_9-6^*a_3-13^*a_4-13^*a_5$	$(-a_{17}-11^*a_{21}-11^*a_{18}-11^*a_{20}-7^*a_{13}-11^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-6^*a_{14}-a_{11}+12^*a_6-11^*a_{16}+2^*m+6^*a_2-12^*a_1-4^*a_{10}+12^*a_7-6^*a_9+6^*a_3+13^*a_4+12^*a_5)$	$a_6+a_3-a_8$	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6-m+a_1+a_{10}+a_8-a_7+a_9-a_3-a_4-a_5$	$m-a_9$	a_9
a21	m-a21	$2^*a_6+m+a_2-a_1-a_{10}-a_8+a_7-a_9+a_3+a_4+2^*a_5-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{14}$	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6-a_2+a_1+a_{10}+a_8-a_7+a_9-a_3-a_4-2^*a_5$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	a_2	m-a2	m-a4	a4	m-a36	a36
a20	m-a20	a8	m-a8	a1	m-a1	a3	m-a3	$(-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{14}+2^*a_6+a_2-a_1-a_{10}+a_7-a_9+a_3+2^*a_4+2^*a_5)$	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6+m-a_2+a_1+a_{10}-a_7+a_9-a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5$	$a_{17}+a_{21}+6^*a_{18}+9^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+6^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}-a_{11}-11^*a_6+9^*a_{16}+a_{12}+3^*m-5^*a_2+10^*a_1+5^*a_{10}+a_8-10^*a_7+5^*a_9-5^*a_3-10^*a_4-11^*a_5$	$(-a_{17}-a_{21}-6^*a_{18}-9^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-6^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}+a_{11}+11^*a_6-9^*a_{16}-12^*a_7+m-5^*a_2-10^*a_1-5^*a_{10}-a_8+10^*a_7-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+11^*a_5)$
a19	m-a19	$a_{17}+11^*a_{21}+11^*a_{18}+11^*a_{20}+7^*a_{13}+11^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+6^*a_{14}+a_{11}-12^*a_6+11^*a_{16}+2^*m-6^*a_2+12^*a_1+4^*a_{10}-11^*a_7+6^*a_9-6^*a_3-12^*a_4-12^*a_5$	$12^*a_6-11^*a_{16}-m+6^*a_2-12^*a_1-4^*a_{10}+11^*a_7-6^*a_9+6^*a_3+12^*a_4+12^*a_5-a_{17}-11^*a_{21}-11^*a_{18}-11^*a_{20}-7^*a_{13}-11^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-6^*a_{14}-a_{11}$	m-a2	a2	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	$6^*a_{18}+8^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+6^*a_{19}+6^*a_{15}+6^*a_{14}-13^*a_6+8^*a_{16}+6^*m-6^*a_2+11^*a_7+6^*a_9-6^*a_3-11^*a_4-12^*a_5$	$(-6^*a_{18}-8^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-6^*a_{19}-6^*a_{15}-6^*a_{14}+13^*a_6-8^*a_{16}-5^*m+6^*a_2-11^*a_7-6^*a_9+6^*a_3+11^*a_4+12^*a_5)$	$(-11^*a_{21}+10^*a_{18}+10^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+10^*a_{19}+3^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}+a_{11}-10^*a_6+11^*a_{16}+a_{39}+2^*m-5^*a_2+10^*a_1+3^*a_{10}-10^*a_7+5^*a_9-5^*a_3-10^*a_4-10^*a_5)$	$(-11^*a_{21}+10^*a_{18}-10^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-10^*a_{19}-3^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}-a_{11}+10^*a_6-11^*a_{16}-a_{39}-m-5^*a_2-10^*a_1-3^*a_{10}+10^*a_7-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+10^*a_5)$
a18	m-a18	$10^*a_6-11^*a_{16}-m+5^*a_2-11^*a_1-3^*a_{10}+10^*a_7-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+11^*a_4+10^*a_5-a_{17}-11^*a_{21}-10^*a_{18}-11^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-10^*a_{19}-4^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}-a_{11}$	$a_{17}+11^*a_{21}+10^*a_{18}+11^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+10^*a_{19}+4^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}+a_{11}-10^*a_6+11^*a_{16}+2^*m-5^*a_2+11^*a_1+3^*a_{10}-10^*a_7+5^*a_9-5^*a_3-11^*a_4-10^*a_5$	m-a3	a3	m-a1	a1	$(-5^*a_{18}-8^*a_{20}-5^*a_{13}-5^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}+11^*a_6-8^*a_{16}-5^*m+5^*a_2-10^*a_1-5^*a_{10}-a_8+10^*a_7-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+10^*a_5)$	$5^*a_{18}+8^*a_{20}+5^*a_{13}+5^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}-11^*a_6+8^*a_{16}+6^*m-5^*a_2+10^*a_1+5^*a_{10}+a_8-10^*a_7+5^*a_9-5^*a_3-10^*a_4-10^*a_5$	m-a39	a39
a17	m-a17	$a_6+a_3-a_8$	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6-m+a_1+a_{10}+a_8-a_7+a_9-a_3-a_4-a_5$	$2^*m-a_6-a_7-a_5$	a7	a6	a5	$3^*m-a_6-a_7-a_2-a_3-a_5-a_4+a_1$	$(-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{14}+2^*a_6+a_2-2^*a_1-a_{10}+2^*a_7-a_9+a_3+2^*a_4+2^*a_5)$	m-a12	a12
a16	m-a16	$m-a_6-a_3+a_8$	$(-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{14}+2^*a_6+2^*m-a_1-a_{10}-a_8+a_7-a_9+a_3+a_4+a_5)$	$a_6+a_7+a_5-m$	m-a7	m-a6	m-a5	$a_6+a_7+a_2+a_3+a_5+a_4-a_1-2^*m$	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6+m-a_2+2^*a_1+a_{10}-2^*a_7+a_9-a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5$	$(-6^*a_{18}-8^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-6^*a_{19}-5^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}+a_{11}+11^*a_6-8^*a_{16}-5^*m+a_{36}+5^*a_2-10^*a_1-5^*a_{10}-a_8+10^*a_7-5^*a_9+5^*a_3+10^*a_4+11^*a_5)$	$6^*a_{18}+8^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+6^*a_{19}+5^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}-a_{11}-11^*a_6+8^*a_{16}+6^*m-a_{36}-5^*a_2+10^*a_1+5^*a_{10}+a_8-10^*a_7+5^*a_9-5^*a_3-10^*a_4-11^*a_5$
$5^*a_{21}+5^*a_{18}+(9/2)^*a_{20}+(7/2)^*a_{13}+5^*a_{19}+(9/2)^*a_{15}+(7/2)^*a_{14}+4^*a_7+5^*a_{16}+(15/2)^*m-(9/2)^*a_2+8^*a_1+(9/2)^*a_{10}-8^*a_7+(9/2)^*a_9-(7/2)^*a_3-8^*a_4-8^*a_5-a_{17}$	$a_{17}-5^*a_{21}-4^*a_{18}-(9/2)^*a_{20}-(5/2)^*a_{13}-4^*a_{19}-(5/2)^*a_{15}-(5/2)^*a_{14}-a_{11}+5^*a_6-5^*a_{16}-(15/2)^*m+(7/2)^*a_2-6^*a_1-(5/2)^*a_{10}+a_8+6^*a_7-(5/2)^*a_9+(5/2)^*a_3+6^*a_4+6^*a_5$	$a_{17}+12^*a_{21}+10^*a_{18}+11^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+10^*a_{19}+3^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}+a_{11}-9^*a_6+12^*a_7-m-4^*a_2+9^*a_1+2^*a_{10}-9^*a_7+4^*a_9-4^*a_3-9^*a_4-9^*a_5$	m-a15	m-a14	m-a13	$12^*a_6-11^*a_{16}-5^*m+6^*a_2-12^*a_1-4^*a_{10}+12^*a_7-6^*a_9+6^*a_3+12^*a_4+12^*a_5-11^*a_{21}-10^*a_{18}-10^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-10^*a_{19}-4^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}-a_{11}$	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6+2^*m-a_2+2^*a_1+a_{10}-2^*a_7+a_9-a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5$	$4^*m-a_{17}-a_{21}-a_{18}-a_{20}-a_{19}+a_{15}+a_{11}-a_6-a_{16}-a_2+a_1+a_{10}-a_7+a_9-a_3-a_4-a_5$	m-a11	m-a10	$2^*a_6+m+a_2-2^*a_1-a_{10}+2^*a_7-2^*a_9+a_3+2^*a_4+2^*a_5-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-2^*a_{15}-a_{14}$
$a_{17}-5^*a_{21}-5^*a_{18}-(9/2)^*a_{20}-(7/2)^*a_{13}-5^*a_{19}-(9/2)^*a_{15}-(7/2)^*a_{14}-a_{11}+7^*a_6-5^*a_{16}-(13/2)^*m+(9/2)^*a_2-8^*a_1-(9/2)^*a_{10}+a_8+8^*a_7-(9/2)^*a_9+(7/2)^*a_3+8^*a_4+8^*a_5$	$5^*a_{21}+4^*a_{18}+(9/2)^*a_{20}+(5/2)^*a_{13}+4^*a_{19}+(5/2)^*a_{15}+(5/2)^*a_{14}+a_{11}-5^*a_6+5^*a_{16}+(17/2)^*m-(7/2)^*a_2+6^*a_1+(5/2)^*a_{10}-a_8-6^*a_7+(5/2)^*a_9-(5/2)^*a_3-6^*a_4-6^*a_5-a_{17}$	$9^*a_6-12^*a_{16}+2^*m+4^*a_2-9^*a_1-2^*a_{10}+9^*a_7-4^*a_9+4^*a_3+9^*a_4+9^*a_5-a_{17}-12^*a_{21}-10^*a_{18}-11^*a_{20}-6^*a_{13}-10^*a_{19}-3^*a_{15}-5^*a_{14}-a_{11}$	a15	a14	a13	$11^*a_{21}+10^*a_{18}+10^*a_{20}+6^*a_{13}+10^*a_{19}+4^*a_{15}+5^*a_{14}+a_{11}-12^*a_6+11^*a_{16}+6^*m-6^*a_2+12^*a_1+4^*a_{10}-12^*a_7+6^*a_9-6^*a_3-12^*a_4-12^*a_5$	$2^*a_6-m+a_2-2^*a_1-a_{10}+2^*a_7-a_9+a_3+2^*a_4+2^*a_5-a_{18}-a_{13}-a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{14}$	$(-3^*m+a_{17}+a_{21}+a_{18}+a_{20}+a_{19}-a_{15}-a_{11}+a_6+a_{16}+a_2-a_1-a_{10}+a_7-a_9+a_3+a_4+a_5)$	a11	a10	$a_{18}+a_{13}+a_{19}+2^*a_{15}+a_{14}-2^*a_6-a_2+2^*a_1+a_{10}-2^*a_7+2^*a_9-a_3-2^*a_4-2^*a_5$

• Details

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal flat-type striped** magic square of order 12 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×12 and two magic rectangles of order 2×8 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8. It is again composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×4 . Inner part is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below an example:

Example 2.12. Below are two examples of **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 12 based on Result 2.12 are given by

12	pan	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444
444	37	232	-4363	2119	226	-287	2372	110	88	31	-2108	1987	444
444	37	-158	4437	-2045	-152	361	-2298	-36	-14	43	2182	-1913	444
444	2122	-2048	-35	220	-2076	2177	-3787	3834	64	-101	-3524	3598	444
444	-2201	2275	109	-146	2150	-2103	3861	-3760	10	175	40	34	444
444	70	4	-140	214	19	55	13	61	55	19	74	0	444
444	67	7	31	43	10	64	16	58	-164	238	2336	-2262	444
444	64	10	3807	-3733	61	13	55	19	2339	-2265	3456	-3382	444
444	61	13	-3550	3624	58	16	64	10	-2082	2156	74	0	444
444	58	16	10	175	73	28	25	22	109	-146	31	43	444
444	55	19	64	-101	1	46	49	52	-35	220	-2191	2265	444
444	2182	-1913	3526	22	25	28	-3604	294	-29	34	37	-158	444
444	-2108	1987	-3452	52	49	46	3678	-220	103	40	37	232	444
444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444	444

It is a **pandiagonal flat-type striped** magic square of order 12 with magic sum $S_{12 \times 12} := 444$. The magic sum of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 is given as $S_{8 \times 8} := 296$ and the magic sum of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 is $S_{4 \times 4} := 148$. The width of each magic rectangle is 74. See below the details:

	pan	296	296	296	296	296	296	296	296	296	296
296	-35	220	-2076	2177	-3787	3834	64	-101	296		
296	109	-146	2150	-2103	3861	-3760	10	175	296		
296	-140	214	19	55	13	61	55	19	296		
296	31	43	10	64	16	58	-164	238	296		
296	3807	-3733	61	13	55	19	2339	-2265	296		
296	-3550	3624	58	16	64	10	-2082	2156	296		
296	10	175	73	28	25	22	109	-146	296		
296	64	-101	1	46	49	52	-35	220	296		
296	296	296	296	296	296	296	296	296	296		

	pan	148	148	148	148
148	19	55	13	61	148
148	10	64	16	58	148
148	61	13	55	19	148
	58	16	64	10	148
	148	148	148	148	148

2.5.3 Corner-Type

Result 2.13. An *algebraic pandiagonal corner-type striped* magic square of order 12 in **cyclic way** is given by

$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	a_4	$m-a_4$	$m-a_6$	a_6	$m-a_9$	a_9	$m-a_{13}$	a_{13}
$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	a_2	a_3	$(1/2)*m+a_2-a_5$	$(1/2)*m-a_2+a_5$	$a_1+a_7-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7$	$a_1+a_{10}+a_7-m$	$2*m-a_1-a_{10}-a_7$	$a_7+a_{14}+a_{10}+a_1-(3/2)*m$	$(5/2)*m-a_7-a_{10}-a_1-a_{14}$
a_2	a_3	$a_1-a_3-a_2+m$	$m-a_1$	$(1/2)*m-a_3-a_2+a_1+a_5$	$a_3+a_2+(1/2)*m-a_1-a_5$	$(1/2)*m+a_1-a_3-a_2+a_8$	$a_3+a_2+(1/2)*m-a_8-a_1$	$a_6-a_{12}+a_8-a_2-a_3+a_4+a_1$	$m-a_6+a_{12}-a_8+a_2+a_3-a_4-a_1$	$(1/2)*m+a_{15}+a_1-a_2-a_3$	$(1/2)*m-a_1+a_2+a_3-a_{15}$
$m-a_2$	$m-a_3$	$a_3+a_2-a_1$	a_1	$m-a_4-a_1+a_3$	$a_4+a_1-a_3$	$m-a_1+a_3-a_4+a_5-a_8$	$a_1-a_3+a_4-a_5+a_8$	$(1/2)*m-a_1+a_{11}$	$(1/2)*m+a_1-a_{11}$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_{17}+a_{11}-a_{10}$	$a_1+a_{17}-a_{11}+a_{10}-(1/2)*m$
$(1/2)*m-a_4-a_1+a_3+a_2$	$a_1-a_2+a_5$	$m-a_5$	$a_4+(1/2)*m-a_3$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7+a_2-a_5$	$a_1+a_7-a_2+a_5-(1/2)*m$	$2*m-a_8+a_2+a_3-a_4-a_{11}-a_1-a_7$	$a_8-a_2-a_3+a_4+a_{11}+a_1+a_7-m$	$2*m-a_4-a_8-a_7-a_{11}-a_{16}+a_{12}-a_1+a_2+a_3$	$a_4+a_8+a_7+a_{11}+a_{16}-a_{12}+a_1-a_2-a_3-m$
$a_4+(1/2)*m+a_1-a_3-a_2$	$(m-a_1+a_2-a_5)$	a_5	$(1/2)*m+a_3-a_4$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$a_6+a_4-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_4-a_6$	a_{12}	$m-a_{12}$	a_{16}	$m-a_{16}$
$a_6+a_3+a_2-a_1-(1/2)*m$	$m-a_7$	$m-a_8$	$(1/2)*m-a_3+a_4-a_5+a_8$	$a_1+a_7-a_2+a_5-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_4-a_6$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$m-a_{10}$	a_{10}	a_{17}	$m-a_{17}$
$(3/2)*m+a_1-a_6-a_3-a_2$	a_7	a_8	$(1/2)*m+a_3-a_4+a_5-a_8$	$(3/2)*m-a_1-a_7+a_2-a_5$	$a_6+a_4-(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m-a_6+a_9$	$(1/2)*m+a_6-a_9$	$a_9+a_4+a_8-a_{12}-a_{15}$	$a_{15}+a_{12}+m-a_4-a_8-a_9$
$a_2+a_3-a_1+a_9-(1/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-a_{10}-a_7$	$(3/2)*m-a_6+a_{12}-a_8-a_4$	$m-a_{11}$	$a_8-a_2-a_3+a_4+a_{11}+a_1+a_7-m$	$m-a_{12}$	a_{10}	$(1/2)*m+a_6-a_9$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$m-a_{14}$	a_{14}
$a_1+(3/2)*m-a_9-a_2-a_3$	$a_{10}+a_7-(1/2)*m$	$a_6-a_{12}+a_8+a_4-(1/2)*m$	a_{11}	$2*m-a_8+a_2+a_3-a_4-a_{11}-a_1-a_7$	a_{12}	$m-a_{10}$	$(1/2)*m-a_6+a_9$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m-a_9+a_{13}$	$(1/2)*m+a_9-a_{13}$
$a_2+a_3+a_{13}-(1/2)*m-a_1$	$2*m-a_7-a_{14}-a_{10}$	$m-a_{15}$	$a_{17}-a_{11}+a_{10}$	$a_4+a_8+a_7+a_1+1+a_{16}-a_{12}+a_1-a_2-a_3-m$	$m-a_{16}$	$m-a_{17}$	$a_{15}+a_{12}+m-a_4-a_8-a_9$	a_{14}	$(1/2)*m+a_9-a_{13}$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$
$(3/2)*m+a_1-a_2-a_3-a_{13}$	$a_7+a_{14}+a_{10}-m$	a_{15}	$m-a_{17}+a_{11}-a_{10}$	$2*m-a_4-a_8-a_7-a_{11}-a_{16}+a_{12}-a_1+a_2+a_3$	a_{16}	a_{17}	$a_9+a_4+a_8-a_{12}-a_{15}$	$m-a_{14}$	$(1/2)*m-a_9+a_{13}$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal corner-type striped** magic square of order 12, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8 and 10 are at the upper-left corner. These magic squares are also **pandiagonals**. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, where **m** is the width of the **strip**. See below an example:

Example 2.13. Below are two examples of **algebraic pandiagonal striped** magic square of order 12 based on Result 2.13 are given by

12	pan	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372
372	19	10	49	46	19	43	37	25	28	34	16	46	372
372	43	52	13	16	22	40	7	55	13	49	31	31	372
372	13	16	43	52	34	28	43	19	13	49	64	-2	372
372	49	46	19	10	49	13	40	22	61	1	28	34	372
372	31	19	40	34	31	31	46	16	25	37	13	49	372
372	31	43	22	28	31	31	13	49	43	19	55	7	372
372	13	34	31	43	16	49	31	31	25	37	58	4	372
372	49	28	31	19	46	13	31	31	40	22	-11	73	372
372	22	28	61	22	37	19	37	22	31	31	13	49	372
372	40	34	1	40	25	43	25	40	31	31	43	19	372
372	34	10	10	55	49	7	4	73	49	19	31	31	372
	28	52	52	7	13	55	58	-11	13	43	31	31	372
	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372

It is a **pandiagonal corner-type striped** magic square of order 12 with magic sum $S_{12 \times 12} := 372$. The magic sum of **pandiagonal** magic square of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are given as $S_{10 \times 10} := 310$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 248$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 186$ and $S_{4 \times 4} := 124$. All are composed of magic rectangles of equal width. The width of each magic rectangle is 62. See below the details:

	pan	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310
310	19	10	49	46	19	43	37	25	28	34	310	
310	43	52	13	16	22	40	7	55	13	49	310	
310	13	16	43	52	34	28	43	19	13	49	310	
310	49	46	19	10	49	13	40	22	61	1	310	
310	31	19	40	34	31	31	46	16	25	37	310	
310	31	43	22	28	31	31	13	49	43	19	310	
310	13	34	31	43	16	49	31	31	25	37	310	
310	49	28	31	19	46	13	31	31	40	22	310	
310	22	28	61	22	37	19	37	22	31	31	310	
	40	34	1	40	25	43	25	40	31	31	310	
	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	

	pan	248	248	248	248	248	248	248	248
248	19	10	49	46	19	43	37	25	248
248	43	52	13	16	22	40	7	55	248
248	13	16	43	52	34	28	43	19	248
248	49	46	19	10	49	13	40	22	248
248	31	19	40	34	31	31	46	16	248
248	31	43	22	28	31	31	13	49	248
248	13	34	31	43	16	49	31	31	248
	49	28	31	19	46	13	31	31	248
	248	248	248	248	248	248	248	248	248

	pan	186	186	186	186	186	186
186	19	10	49	46	19	43	186
186	43	52	13	16	22	40	186
186	13	16	43	52	34	28	186
186	49	46	19	10	49	13	186
186	31	19	40	34	31	31	186
	31	43	22	28	31	31	186
	186	186	186	186	186	186	186

	pan	124	124	124	124
124	19	10	49	46	124
124	43	52	13	16	124
124	13	16	43	52	124
	49	46	19	10	124
	124	124	124	124	124

3 Algebraic Pandiagonal Semi-Striped Magic Squares

The above section is dedicated to even orders magic squares. In this section we shall work with odd orders **algebraic pandiagonal semi-striped** magic squares. We call these as **semi-striped** as all of them contain either magic square of order 3 or 5. Except these two the other parts are formed by strips, i.e., by magic rectangles of equal width 2. Most of the results of orders 8, 10 and 12 are of three types. Here, these results for the orders 7, 9 and 11 are of two types, i.e., **cyclic** and **cornered**. The order 5 is only **corner-type**.

In the previous section, we worked with three types of **algebraic pandiagonal striped**, i.e., these are **cyclic-type**, **flat-type** and **corner-type**. Here we shall work with only two types, i.e., **cyclic-type** and **corner-type**. The reason is that we don't have good results for the **flat-type** case.

3.1 Algebraic Pandiagonal Semi-Striped Magic Square of Order 5

Below is a result of **pandiagonal corner-type** magic square of order 5.

3.1.1 Corner-Type

Result 3.1. An **algebraic pandiagonal semi-striped** magic square of order 5 is given by

a_2	$m-2*a_2$	a_2	a_1	$2*m/3-a_1$
$m/3$	$m/3$	$m/3$	$m/3$	$m/3$
$2*m/3-a_2$	$2*a_2-m/3$	$2*m/3-a_2$	$2*m/3-a_1$	a_1
$m-a_1-a_2$	$m/3$	$a_1+m/3-a_2$	a_2	a_2
$a_1+a_2-m/3$	$m/3$	$m/3-a_1+a_2$	$2*m/3-a_2$	$2*m/3-a_2$

• Details

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 5, where the magic square of order 3 is at the upper-left corner. Moreover, it has two magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×5 . In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := m$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5m}{3}$. Since the magic rectangles width is proportional to magic square of order 3, it requires that the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. It is to avoid fractional entries. See below an example:

Example 3.1. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 5 based on Result 3.1:

	pan	45	45	45	45	45
45	14	-1	14	11	7	45
45	9	9	9	9	9	45
45	4	19	4	7	11	45
45	2	9	6	14	14	45
	16	9	12	4	4	45
	45	45	45	45	45	45

In this case the magic sum of orders 5 and 3 are $S_{5 \times 5} := 45$ and $S_{3 \times 3} := 27$. The magic square of order 5 is **pandiagonal** and magic square of order 3 is a normal magic square. See below:

3	mgc			27
	14	-1	14	27
	9	9	9	27
	4	19	4	27
	27	27	27	27

3.2 Algebraic Pandiagonal Semi-Striped Magic Square of Order 7

In this subsection, we shall present two different ways of representing **algebraic pandiagonal semi-striped** magic square of order 7. These are **cyclic** and **cornered** types.

3.2.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 3.2. An **algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped** magic square of order 7 is given by

$S-a_3-a_1$	a_3	a_4	a_5	$(2/3)*S+a_1-a_4-a_5$	$(2/3)*S-a_6$	a_6
$a_3+a_1-(1/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a_3$	$(2/3)*S-a_4$	$(2/3)*S-a_5$	$a_4+a_5-a_1$	$a_1+a_2+a_6-(2/3)*S$	$(4/3)*S-a_1-a_2-a_6$
$(2/3)*S-a_4$	a_4	$a_1+a_2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_2$	$2*S/3-a_1$	$(2/3)*S+a_1-a_4-a_5$	$a_4+a_5-a_1$
$S-a_3-a_5$	$a_3+a_5-(1/3)*S$	$4*S/3-2*a_1-a_2$	$S/3$	$2*a_1+a_2-2*S/3$	$S-a_1-a_2-a_6+a_5$	$a_1+a_2+a_6-a_5-(1/3)*S$
$a_3+a_5-a_2-a_1+a_4$	$(2/3)*S-a_3-a_5+a_2+a_1-a_4$	a_1	a_2	$S-a_1-a_2$	$a_6+a_4-a_1$	$(2/3)*S+a_1-a_6-a_4$
$a_1+a_2+a_6-(2/3)*S$	$(4/3)*S-a_1-a_2-a_6$	$a_3+a_5-a_2-a_1+a_4$	$a_1+a_2+a_6-a_5-a_3$	$(2/3)*S+a_1-a_6-a_4$	a_3	$S-a_3-a_1$
$(2/3)*S-a_6$	a_6	$(2/3)*S-a_3-a_5+a_2+a_1-a_4$	$(2/3)*S+a_3-a_1-a_2-a_6+a_5$	$a_6+a_4-a_1$	$(2/3)*S-a_3$	$a_3+a_1-(1/3)*S$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped** magic square of order 7 embedded with a magic square of order 3. Moreover, there are four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×5 . In this case, the magic sums are $M_{3 \times 3} := S$ and $M_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$. Since the magic rectangle's width is proportional to magic square of order 3, it requires that the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. It is to avoid fractional entries. See below an example:

Example 3.2. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped** magic square of order 7 based on Result 3.2:

	pan	77						
77	7	16	19	22	-9	-3	25	77
77	15	6	3	0	31	26	-4	77
77	3	19	12	9	12	-9	31	77
77	-5	27	11	11	11	7	15	77
77	34	-12	10	13	10	34	-12	77
77	26	-4	34	10	-12	16	7	77
	-3	25	-12	12	34	6	15	77
	77	77	77	77	77	77	77	77

In this case the magic sum of orders 7 and 3 are $M_{7 \times 7} := 77$ and $M_{3 \times 3} := 33$. The magic square of order 7 is **pandiagonal** and magic square of order 3 is a normal magic square. See below:

3	mgc			33
	12	9	12	33
	11	11	11	33
	10	13	10	33
	33	33	33	33

3.2.2 Corner-Type

Result 3.3. An **algebraic pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 7 is given by

a1	a2	S-a1-a2-a3-a4	a3	a4	(2/5)*S-a8	a8
a7-a2+(1/5)*S	a5	a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-(1/5)*S	a6	S-a1-a3-a4-a7	a9	(2/5)*S-a9
a2+a3+a4-a5-(1/5)*S	S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a7	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S-a2-a3+a5+a7	a1+a2+a3-a6-(1/5)*S	a7-(1/5)*S+a4	(3/5)*S-a7-a4
(1/5)*S-a3+a5	a1-a6+a7	a2+a3-(1/5)*S	(4/5)*S-a1-a5-a7	(1/5)*S-a2+a6	(2/5)*S-a9	a9
S-a1-a4-(1/5)*S-a7	a3+a4-a5	(1/5)*S-a2-a3+a5+a6	a1+a2-a6	a7	a8-a7+(2/5)*S-a4	a7+a4-a8
a8+a1-(1/5)*S	a1+a7-a9	(3/5)*S-a1-a4	(2/5)*S+a9-a1-a7	(1/5)*S+a4-a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S
(3/5)*S-a1-a8	(2/5)*S+a9-a1-a7	a1+a4-(1/5)*S	a1+a7-a9	(1/5)*S-a4+a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S

- Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 7, where magic square of order 5 is at the upper-left corner. Except the magic square of order 5, the rest are **magic rectangles** of width 2 and different lengths. Due to this we call it as a **semi-striped** magic square. In this case, the magic sums are $M_{5 \times 5} := S$ and $M_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{5}$. Since the magic rectangle's width is proportional to magic square

of order 5, it requires that the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. It is to avoid fractional entries. See below an example:

Example 3.3. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 7 based on Result 3.3:

	pan	56	56	56	56	56	56	56
56	10	13	-18	16	19	-15	31	56
56	23	22	3	25	-33	34	-18	56
56	18	-21	8	29	6	39	-23	56
56	14	13	21	-28	20	-18	34	56
56	-25	13	26	-2	28	0	16	56
56	33	4	-5	12	-4	8	8	56
	-17	12	21	4	20	8	8	56
	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	56

In this case the magic sum of orders 7 and 5 are $M_{7 \times 7} := 56$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := 40$. The magic squares of orders 5 and 7 both are **pandiagonal** See below:

	pan	40	40	40	40	40
40	10	13	-18	16	19	40
40	23	22	3	25	-33	40
40	18	-21	8	29	6	40
40	14	13	21	-28	20	40
	-25	13	26	-2	28	40
	40	40	40	40	40	40

Remark 3.1. In this case we considered directly, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 instead of considering as **corner-type** magic square of order 5 as given in Result 3.1. The reason for not considering is that the results becomes very obvious. See below:

m/3	m/3	m/3	a1	2*m/3-a1	2*m/3-a2	a2
m/3	m/3	m/3	m/3	m/3	2*m/3-a3	a3
m/3	m/3	m/3	2*m/3-a1	a1	2*m/3-a1	a1
2*m/3-a1	m/3	a1	m/3	m/3	a3	m-m/3-a3
a1	m/3	2*m/3-a1	m/3	m/3	a2+a1-m/3	m-a1-a2
a2	a3	a1	2*m/3-a3	m-a1-a2	m/3	m/3
m-a2-m/3	2*m/3-a3	2*m/3-a1	a3	a2+a1-m/3	m/3	m/3

We have only 3 possibilities to choose 49 entries. The magic sums of order 3 becomes equal value entries. See below an example:

	pan	119	119	119	119	119	119	119
119	17	17	17	11	23	20	14	119
119	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	119
119	17	17	17	23	11	23	11	119
119	23	17	11	17	17	17	17	119
119	11	17	23	17	17	8	26	119
119	14	17	11	17	26	17	17	119
	20	17	23	17	8	17	17	119
	119	119	119	119	119	119	119	119

	pan	85	85	85	85	85
85	17	17	17	11	23	85
85	17	17	17	17	17	85
85	17	17	17	23	11	85
85	23	17	11	17	17	85
	11	17	23	17	17	85
	85	85	85	85	85	85

	pan	85	85	85	85	85
85	17	17	17	11	23	85
85	17	17	17	17	17	85
85	17	17	17	23	11	85
85	23	17	11	17	17	85
	11	17	23	17	17	85
	85	85	85	85	85	85

In the above example the magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are **pandiagonal** and magic square of order 3 is only with single entry. Due to this, we shall work directly with magic square of order 5 instead of **cornered** magic square of order 5.

3.3 Algebraic Pandiagonal Semi-Striped Magic Squares of Order 9

In this subsection, we shall present two different ways of representing **algebraic pandiagonal semi-striped** magic square of order 9. These are **cyclic** and **cornered** types.

3.3.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 3.4. An **algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped** magic square of order 9 is given by

a9	$(2/5)*S-a9$	a10	a11	a12	$(1/5)*S-a9-a10-a11-a12$	$(4/5)*S+a9$	$2*S/5-a13$	a13
$2*S/5-a9$	a9	$2*S/5-a10$	$2*S/5-a11$	$2*S/5-a12$	$(1/5)*S+a9+a10+a11+a12$	$(-a9-(2/5)*S)$	a13	$(2/5)*S-a13$
$a8+a7+(2/5)*S-a10-a12-a15$	$a15-a8-a7+a10+a12$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4$	a3	a4	$2*S/5-a14$	a14
$a8+a1-a11$	$(2/5)*S+a11-a8-a1$	$a8-a2+a7$	a5	$a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-a7$	a6	$S-a1-a3-a4-a8$	$a8+a7+a1-a9-a10-a11-a12-(2/5)*S$	$(4/5)*S-a8-a7-a1+a9+a10+a11+a12$
a15	$2*S/5-a15$	$a2+a3+a4-a5-a7$	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a8$	a7	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a8$	$a1+a2+a3-a6-a7$	$a4+a8+a1+a14+a12+a9-(1/5)*S$	$(3/5)*S-a4-a8-a1-a9-a14-a12$
$(3/5)*S+2*a9-a1-a8-a7+a10+a11+a12$	$a1+a8+a7-a10-a11-a12-(1/5)*S-2*a9$	$a7-a3+a5$	$a1-a6+a8$	$a2+a3-a7$	$S-a1-a5-a7-a8$	$a7-a2+a6$	$(3/5)*S+a11-a8-a1-a13$	$a8+a1+a13-(1/5)*S-a11$
$(-2*a9-a8)$	$(2/5)*S+2*a9+a8$	$S-a1-a4-a7-a8$	$a3+a4-a5$	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a6$	$a1+a2-a6$	a8	$a13+(3/5)*S+a10-a4-a8-a7-a1$	$a4+a8+a7+a1-a13-(1/5)*S-a10$
a13	$(2/5)*S-a13$	$a1+a14-a9$	$2*a9+a10+a11+a12$	$a15-a4-a8-a7-a1-a9+(2/5)*S-a14$	$a13+(1/5)*S-a11$	$a4+a8+a7-a13+(2/5)*S-a10-a12-a15$	$2*S/5-a9$	a9
$(2/5)*S-a13$	a13	$(2/5)*S-a1-a14+a9$	$(2/5)*S-2*a9-a10-a11-a12$	$a4+a8+a7+a1+a9+a14-a15$	$(1/5)*S+a11-a13$	$a15-a4-a8-a7+a13+a10+a12$	a9	$(2/5)*S-a9$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped** magic square of order 9 embedded with a pandiagonal magic square of order 5. Moreover, there are four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×7 . In this case, the magic sums are $M_{5 \times 5} := S$ and $M_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$. Since the magic rectangle's width is proportional to magic square of order 5, it requires that the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. It is to avoid fractional entries. See below an example:

Example 3.4. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped** magic square of order 9 based on Result 3.4:

	pan	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99
99	32	-10	35	38	41	-135	76	-22	44	99
99	-10	32	-13	-16	-19	157	-54	44	-22	99
99	-49	71	8	11	5	14	17	-25	47	99
99	-1	23	44	20	-19	23	-13	-105	127	99
99	50	-28	-4	-1	26	50	-16	163	-141	99
99	148	-126	32	14	-1	-28	38	-10	32	99
99	-93	115	-25	11	44	-4	29	32	-10	99
99	44	-22	23	178	-87	17	-76	-10	32	99
	-22	44	-1	-156	109	5	98	32	-10	99
	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99

In this case the magic sum of orders 9 and 5 are $M_{9 \times 9} := 99$ and $M_{5 \times 5} := 55$. The magic square of orders 9 and 5 both are **pandiagonals** See below:

	pan	55	55	55	55	55
55	8	11	5	14	17	55
55	44	20	-19	23	-13	55
55	-4	-1	26	50	-16	55
55	32	14	-1	-28	38	55
	-25	11	44	-4	29	55
	55	55	55	55	55	55

3.3.2 Corner-Type

Result 3.5. An **algebraic pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 9 is given by

a1	a2	S-a1-a2-a3-a4	a3	a4	(2/5)*S-a8	a8	2*S/5-a10	a10
a7-a2+(1/5)*S	a5	a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-(1/5)*S	a6	S-a1-a3-a4-a7	a9	(2/5)*S-a9	2*S/5-a11	a11
a2+a3+a4-a5-(1/5)*S	S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a7	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S-a2-a3+a5+a7	a1+a2+a3-a6-(1/5)*S	a7-(1/5)*S+a4	(3/5)*S-a7-a4	2*S/5-a12	a12
(1/5)*S-a3+a5	a1-a6+a7	a2+a3-(1/5)*S	(4/5)*S-a1-a5-a7	(1/5)*S-a2+a6	(2/5)*S-a9	a9	2*S/5-a9	a9
S-a1-a4-(1/5)*S-a7	a3+a4-a5	(1/5)*S-a2-a3+a5+a6	a1+a2-a6	a7	a8-a7+(2/5)*S-a4	a7+a4-a8	a12+a8-(1/5)*S	(3/5)*S-a9-a12-a8+a9
a8+a1-(1/5)*S	a1+a7-a9	(3/5)*S-a1-a4	(2/5)*S+a9-a1-a7	(1/5)*S+a4-a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S	a9+a11-(1/5)*S	(3/5)*S-a9-a11
(3/5)*S-a1-a8	(2/5)*S+a9-a1-a7	a1+a4-(1/5)*S	a1+a7-a9	(1/5)*S-a4+a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S+a10-a8	(1/5)*S-a10+a8
a10+a1-(1/5)*S	a11+a1+a7-(2/5)*S	a12+a7-a1	(2/5)*S-a7+a9-a1	(4/5)*S-a12-a8-a7	(3/5)*S-a9-a11	(1/5)*S-a10+a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S
(3/5)*S-a1-a10	(4/5)*S-a11-a1-a7	(2/5)*S+a1-a12-a7	a7-a9+a1	a12+a8+a7-(2/5)*S	a9+a11-(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S+a10-a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S

• Details

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 9, where magic squares of orders 7 and 5 is at the upper-left corners. Both are the magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are also **pandiagonal**. Except the magic square of order 5, the rest are **magic rectangles** of width 2 with different lengths. Due to this we call it as a **semi-striped** magic square. In this case, the magic sums are $M_{5 \times 5} := S$, $M_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{5}$ and $M_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$. Since the magic rectangle's width is proportional to magic square of order 5, it requires that the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. It is to avoid fractional entries. See below an example:

Example 3.5. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 9 based on Result 3.5:

	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
90	10	13	-8	16	19	-11	31	-17	37	90
90	25	22	1	25	-23	34	-14	-20	40	90
90	16	-11	10	31	4	37	-17	-23	43	90
90	16	13	19	-20	22	-14	34	-14	34	90
90	-17	13	28	-2	28	4	16	64	-44	90
90	31	4	1	16	-2	10	10	64	-44	90
90	-11	16	19	4	22	10	10	16	4	90
90	37	58	61	16	-62	-44	4	10	10	90
	-17	-38	-41	4	82	64	16	10	10	90
	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

In this case the magic sum of orders 9, 7 and 5 are $M_{9 \times 9} := 90$, $M_{7 \times 7} := 70$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := 50$. The magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 9 all are **pandiagonals** See below:

	pan	70	70	70	70	70	70	70
70	10	13	-8	16	19	-11	31	70
70	25	22	1	25	-23	34	-14	70
70	16	-11	10	31	4	37	-17	70
70	16	13	19	-20	22	-14	34	70
70	-17	13	28	-2	28	4	16	70
70	31	4	1	16	-2	10	10	70
	-11	16	19	4	22	10	10	70
	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70

	pan	50	50	50	50	50
50	10	13	-8	16	19	50
50	25	22	1	25	-23	50
50	16	-11	10	31	4	50
50	16	13	19	-20	22	50
	-17	13	28	-2	28	50
	50	50	50	50	50	50

3.4 Algebraic Pandiagonal Semi-Striped Magic Squares of Order 11

In this subsection, we shall present two different ways of representing **algebraic pandiagonal semi-striped** magic square of order 11. These are **cyclic** and **cornered** types.

3.4.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 3.6. *An algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped magic square of order 11 is given by*

a_7	$(2/3)*S-a_7$	a_8	a_9	$3*S-5*a_7+a_1$	a_{10}	a_{11}	a_{12}	$5*a_7-a_8-a_9-a_{10}-a_{11}-a_{12}-(2/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a_{13}$	a_{13}
$(2/3)*S-a_7$	a_7	$(2/3)*S-a_8$	$(2/3)*S-a_9$	$5*a_7-a_1-(7/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a_{10}$	$(2/3)*S-a_{11}$	$(2/3)*S-a_{12}$	$(4/3)*S+a_8+a_9+a_{10}+a_{11}+a_{12}-5*a_7$	a_{13}	$(2/3)*S-a_{13}$
$(2/3)*S+a_{13}-a_6-a_{16}$	$a_{16}-a_7-a_{13}+a_6+a_7$	$S-a_3-a_1$	a_3	a_4	a_5	$(2/3)*S+a_1-a_4-a_5$	$(2/3)*S-a_6$	a_6	$(2/3)*S-a_{14}$	a_{14}
$a_2-a_{13}-a_{17}+a_6+a_1$	$(2/3)*S+a_{13}+a_{17}-a_6-a_1-a_2$	$a_3+a_1-(1/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a_3$	$(2/3)*S-a_4$	$(2/3)*S-a_5$	$a_4+a_5-a_1$	$a_1+a_2+a_6-(2/3)*S$	$(4/3)*S-a_1-a_2-a_6$	$(2/3)*S-a_{15}$	a_{15}
a_3+5*a_7-3*S	$(11/3)*S-a_3-5*a_7$	$(2/3)*S-a_4$	a_4	$a_1+a_2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_2$	$2*S/3-a_1$	$(2/3)*S+a_1-a_4-a_5$	$a_4+a_5-a_1$	$a_{11}+a_6-(1/3)*S$	$S-a_{11}-a_6$
$a_{17}-a_3+(5/3)*S-a_2+a_{13}-a_9-a_6-a_1-a_{10}$	$a_3-S+a_2-a_{13}+a_9+a_6+a_1+a_{10}-a_{17}$	$S-a_3-a_5$	$a_3+a_5-(1/3)*S$	$4*S/3-2*a_1-a_2$	$S/3$	$2*a_1+a_2-2*S/3$	$S-a_1-a_2-a_6+a_5$	$a_1+a_2+a_6-a_5-(1/3)*S$	$(1/3)*S-a_2-a_6-a_{11}+a_{12}+a_{15}+a_{10}$	$a_2-a_{12}-a_{15}+a_6-a_{10}+a_1+(1/3)*S$
$(2/3)*S-a_{13}+a_{16}-a_8+a_6-a_{11}$	$a_{13}-a_{16}+a_8-a_6+a_{11}$	$a_3+a_5-a_2-a_1+a_4$	$(2/3)*S-a_3-a_5+a_2+a_1-a_4$	a_1	a_2	$S-a_1-a_2$	$a_6+a_4-a_1$	$(2/3)*S+a_1-a_6-a_4$	$(5/3)*S-a_8-a_9-a_{12}-a_{11}-a_{10}+a_{14}$	$a_8+a_9-S+a_{12}+a_{11}+a_{10}-a_{14}$
$a_7-a_{12}+a_3$	$a_{12}+(2/3)*S-a_3-a_7$	$a_1+a_2+a_6-(2/3)*S$	$(4/3)*S-a_1-a_2-a_6$	$a_3+a_5-a_2-a_1+a_4$	$a_1+a_2+a_6-a_5-a_3$	$(2/3)*S+a_1-a_6-a_4$	a_3	$S-a_3-a_1$	$a_2-a_{13}+a_9+a_6+a_1-(2/3)*S$	$(4/3)*S-a_2+a_{13}-a_9-a_6-a_1$
$(7/3)*S-6*a_7+a_8-a_3+a_9+a_{12}+a_{11}+a_{10}$	$6*a_7-a_8+a_3-a_9-a_{12}-a_{11}-a_{10}-(5/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a_6$	a_6	$(2/3)*S-a_3-a_5+a_2+a_1-a_4$	$(2/3)*S+a_3-a_1-a_2-a_6+a_5$	$a_6+a_4-a_1$	$(2/3)*S-a_3$	$a_3+a_1-(1/3)*S$	$a_8+a_{13}-a_6$	$(2/3)*S-a_{13}-a_8+a_6$
a_{13}	$(2/3)*S-a_{13}$	$S-a_3+a_{14}-a_1-a_7$	$a_3+a_{15}-(2/3)*S+a_7$	$a_{16}-a_8-a_{13}+S-a_{11}$	$a_{17}+(4/3)*S+a_{13}-a_9-a_{12}-a_{15}-a_{10}-a_3$	$a_8+a_3+a_9+a_{12}+a_{11}+a_{10}-a_{14}+a_1-(5/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a_{17}$	$(2/3)*S-a_{16}$	$(2/3)*S-a_7$	a_7
$(2/3)*S-a_{13}$	a_{13}	$a_3-a_{14}+a_1+a_7-(1/3)*S$	$(4/3)*S-a_3-a_{15}-a_7$	$a_8+a_{13}+a_{11}-(1/3)*S-a_{16}$	$a_9+a_{12}+a_{15}+a_{10}+a_3-a_{17}-(2/3)*S-a_{13}$	$a_{14}-a_1+(7/3)*S-a_8-a_3-a_9-a_{12}-a_{11}-a_{10}$	a_{17}	a_{16}	a_7	$(2/3)*S-a_7$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped** magic square of order 9 embedded with pandiagonal magic squares of orders 7 and 3. Moreover, there are four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×9 . In this case, the magic sums are $M_{3 \times 3} := S$, $M_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$ and $M_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$. Since the magic rectangle's width is proportional to magic square of order 3, it requires that the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. It is to avoid fractional entries. See below an example:

Example 3.6. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal cyclic-type semi-striped** magic square of order 9 based on Result 3.6:

	pan	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
209	28	10	31	34	41	37	40	43	-93	-8	46	209
209	10	28	7	4	-3	1	-2	-5	131	46	-8	209
209	4	34	31	16	19	22	7	13	25	-11	49	209
209	-56	94	7	22	19	16	31	10	28	-14	52	209
209	-15	53	19	19	4	25	28	7	31	46	-8	209
209	64	-26	19	19	43	19	-5	31	7	103	-65	209
209	1	37	34	4	10	13	34	34	4	-41	79	209
209	1	37	10	28	34	10	4	16	31	-2	40	209
209	134	-96	13	25	4	28	34	22	7	52	-14	209
209	46	-8	52	58	-5	-2	67	-20	-17	10	28	209
	-8	46	-14	-20	43	40	-29	58	55	28	10	209
	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

In this case the magic sum of orders 11, 7 and 3 are $M_{11 \times 11} := 209$, $M_{7 \times 7} := 133$ and $M_{3 \times 3} := 57$. The magic square of orders 11 and 7 are **pandiagonals** See below:

	pan	133	133	133	133	133	133	133
133	31	16	19	22	7	13	25	133
133	7	22	19	16	31	10	28	133
133	19	19	4	25	28	7	31	133
133	19	19	43	19	-5	31	7	133
133	34	4	10	13	34	34	4	133
133	10	28	34	10	4	16	31	133
	13	25	4	28	34	22	7	133
	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133

3	mgc		57
	4	25	28
	43	19	-5
	10	13	34
	57	57	57

3.4.2 Corner-Type

Result 3.7. An *algebraic pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped* magic square of order 11 is given by

a1	a2	S-a1-a2-a3-a4	a3	a4	(2/5)*S-a8	a8	2*S/5-a10	a10	2*S/5-a13	a13
a7-a2+(1/5)*S	a5	a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-(1/5)*S	a6	S-a1-a3-a4-a7	a9	(2/5)*S-a9	2*S/5-a11	a11	2*S/5-a14	a14
a2+a3+a4-a5-(1/5)*S	S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a7	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S-a2-a3+a5+a7	a1+a2+a3-a6-(1/5)*S	a7-(1/5)*S+a4	(3/5)*S-a7-a4	2*S/5-a12	a12	2*S/5-a15	a15
(1/5)*S-a3+a5	a1-a6+a7	a2+a3-(1/5)*S	(4/5)*S-a1-a5-a7	(1/5)*S-a2+a6	(2/5)*S-a9	a9	2*S/5-a9	a9	2*S/5-a16	a16
S-a1-a4-(1/5)*S-a7	a3+a4-a5	(1/5)*S-a2-a3+a5+a6	a1+a2-a6	a7	a8-a7+(2/5)*S-a4	a7+a4-a8	a12+a8-(1/5)*S	(3/5)*S-a9-a12-a8+a9	a12+a8-(1/5)*S	(3/5)*S-a12-a8
a8+a1-(1/5)*S	a1+a7-a9	(3/5)*S-a1-a4	(2/5)*S+a9-a1-a7	(1/5)*S+a4-a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S	a9+a11-(1/5)*S	(3/5)*S-a9-a11	a11+a16-(1/5)*S	(3/5)*S-a11-a16
(3/5)*S-a1-a8	(2/5)*S+a9-a1-a7	a1+a4-(1/5)*S	a1+a7-a9	(1/5)*S-a4+a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S+a10-a8	(1/5)*S-a10+a8	(1/5)*S-a12-a8+a15+a10	(1/5)*S+a12+a8-a15-a10
a10+a1-(1/5)*S	a11+a1+a7-(2/5)*S	a12+a7-a1	(2/5)*S-a7+a9-a1	(4/5)*S-a12-a8-a7	(3/5)*S-a9-a11	(1/5)*S-a10+a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S-a11+a14	(1/5)*S+a11-a14
(3/5)*S-a1-a10	(4/5)*S-a11-a1-a7	(2/5)*S+a1-a12-a7	a7-a9+a1	a12+a8+a7-(2/5)*S	a9+a11-(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S+a10-a8	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S+a13-a10	(1/5)*S-a13+a10
a13+a1-(1/5)*S	a14+a1+a7-(2/5)*S	a15+a7-a1	(2/5)*S-a1-a7+a16	(4/5)*S-a12-a8-a7	(3/5)*S-a11-a16	(1/5)*S+a12+a8-a15-a10	(1/5)*S+a11-a14	(1/5)*S-a13+a10	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S
(3/5)*S-a1-a13	(4/5)*S-a14-a1-a7	(2/5)*S+a1-a15-a7	a1+a7-a16	a12+a8+a7-(2/5)*S	a11+a16-(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S-a12-a8+a15+a10	(1/5)*S-a11+a14	(1/5)*S+a13-a10	(1/5)*S	(1/5)*S

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 11, where magic squares of orders 9, 7 and 5 are at the upper-left corners. These are also **pandiagonal** magic squares. Except the order 5, the rest are **magic rectangles** of width 2 with different lengths. Due to this we call it as a **semi-striped** magic square of order 11. In this case, the magic sums are $M_{5 \times 5} := S$, $M_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{5}$, $M_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$ and $M_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{5}$. Since the magic rectangle's width is proportional to magic square of order 5, it requires that the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. It is to avoid fractional entries. See below an example:

Example 3.7. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal corner-type semi-striped** magic square of order 11 based on Result 3.7:

	pan	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	
143		10	13	7	16	19	-5	31	-11	37	-20	46	143
143		28	22	-2	25	-8	34	-8	-14	40	-23	49	143
143		13	4	13	34	1	34	-8	-17	43	-26	52	143
143		19	13	16	-8	25	-8	34	-8	34	-29	55	143
143		-5	13	31	-2	28	10	16	61	-35	61	-35	143
143		28	4	10	22	1	13	13	61	-35	82	-56	143
143		-2	22	16	4	25	13	13	19	7	28	-2	143
143		34	52	61	22	-50	-35	7	13	13	22	4	143
143		-8	-26	-35	4	76	61	19	13	13	22	4	143
143		43	61	70	43	-50	-56	-2	4	4	13	13	143
		-17	-35	-44	-17	76	82	28	22	22	13	13	143
		143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143

In this case the magic sum of orders 11, 9, 7 and 5 are $M_{11 \times 11} := 143$, $M_{9 \times 9} := 117$, $M_{7 \times 7} := 91$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := 65$. The magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 all are **pandiagonals** See below:

	pan	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117
117		10	13	7	16	19	-5	31	-11	37	117
117		28	22	-2	25	-8	34	-8	-14	40	117
117		13	4	13	34	1	34	-8	-17	43	117
117		19	13	16	-8	25	-8	34	-8	34	117
117		-5	13	31	-2	28	10	16	61	-35	117
117		28	4	10	22	1	13	13	61	-35	117
117		-2	22	16	4	25	13	13	19	7	117
117		34	52	61	22	-50	-35	7	13	13	117
		-8	-26	-35	4	76	61	19	13	13	117
		117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117

	pan	91	91	91	91	91	91	91
91	10	13	7	16	19	-5	31	91
91	28	22	-2	25	-8	34	-8	91
91	13	4	13	34	1	34	-8	91
91	19	13	16	-8	25	-8	34	91
91	-5	13	31	-2	28	10	16	91
91	28	4	10	22	1	13	13	91
	-2	22	16	4	25	13	13	91
	91	91	91	91	91	91	91	91

	pan	65	65	65	65	65
65	10	13	7	16	19	65
65	28	22	-2	25	-8	65
65	13	4	13	34	1	65
65	19	13	16	-8	25	65
	-5	13	31	-2	28	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

4 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author’s contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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